

Extinction, Climate and Food Security, or Simply Soil and Worms: Heart of the Issue, Source of the Problem... and the Solution (albeit Land is no Longer a Carbon Sink)

Robert J. Blakemore PhD; VermEcology Japan; IUCN; IPBES; rob.blakemore@gmail.com.

Abstract: Soil, with 30,000 Gt SOC (Gigatonnes of Soil Organic Carbon), is the greatest global store of active carbon recently flipped from the major sink to net source of excess atmospheric CO₂. Soil Respiration/decay (~220 Gt C/yr) is twenty times Fossil Fuel (FF) emissions (~10 Gt C/yr). Soil supports >99.9% of species biodiversity (mainly microbes), provides ~99% of human food, and filters 100% of our drinkable freshwater (via earthworm burrows). Soil is yet the most neglected Biome as are its main monitors and mediators, the resident earthworms. These are silently dying, just as soil is being eroded and degraded at irreplaceable rates, to our, and all other species', detriment. Land use change (LUC) releases carbon from deforestation/deserts and soil erosion/poisoning at rates about twice FF emissions, themselves twice CO₂ increase (5 Gt C/yr). Realizing this provides a ready solution to Climate, to Food Security as well as the most pressing of issues: rapid and irreversible species' Extinction. Based upon proper Scientific context and urgent triage priority, an imperative is to redirect all our efforts and funding to restore topsoil. The simplest remedies, available to anyone, are to vermi-compost, to demand or support 100% Organic food (thus protecting earthworms), and to reduce red-meat glut. In this way rich soil humus revives, deforestation reduces and toxic poisoning of our air, water, soil and food is resolved. Organic husbandry within broader Permaculture design principles allows practical and proven solutions to the ecologically interlinked problems.

Keywords: Organic C, soil health, CO₂, productivity, climate, desert, worms, Rothamsted.

1 Introduction

This report aims to scrutinize the critical interlinked issues of Climate Change and Food Security – with Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) being foundational for both – and the relationship of these to the current 6th Global Extinction Event. In recent decades biotic biomass and biodiversity have declined rapidly by up to 70–80%, attributed mainly to intensive agriculture (Blakemore 2018a, IPBES 2019). Two recent papers (Blakemore 2024, 2025) revised Soil Biomass Carbon (30,000 Gt SOC) and Soil species biodiversity (99.9% of global total) while noting rapid topsoil erosion and biotic extinction loss. These new facts about soils may surprise some readers although they are drawn from rational ecological conclusions. The present review synthesis is logistically divided into two main topics: 1/. Climate and 2/. Food. The aims are threefold: To provide a status quo of the currently accepted knowledge; to identify the major issues; and to determine the best methods to remedy these (i.e., in Context with Triage). An immediate answer is to reduce both deforestation and erosion via Soil restoration, allowing the land to recover and to re-sequester Carbon. This is quite simple to achieve: Firstly, reduce excessive red-meat consumption; secondly, restore Organic farming; and, thirdly, practice Permaculture.

Obstacles to progress are primarily our ignorance of basic Soil data due to compromised Science which has become more banal, venal and sadly partisan. This lack of proper scientific investigation of key Soil issues is a major problem preventing appropriate policy. From this, people make poor diet choices allowing destructive agricultural practices to persist. A contrary view by Moinet et al. (2023) argues that Soil is not the only solution but, understandably, they too lack a full catalogue of stocks, losses and capacities. For example, they claim a soil stock as just 1,700 Gt SOC, echoing 4p1000.org who have 1,417 Gt SOC, whereas full estimation is >30,000 Gt SOC, or nearly x20 greater.

Poor farming is responsible for clearing of forests (mainly for meat), for loss of vital topsoil, and for toxic pollution of our air, water, soils as well as the food produced; farming is thus where the solution to these problems may be sought. Restoration of sustainable farming fixes CO₂ excess, catastrophic species loss, as well as issues of human ill-health.

This report will show that, rather than just Fossil Fuel (FF) emissions, the loss of topsoil due to land use change (LUC) mainly for agriculture has contributed much more CO₂ over the same time periods. This is supported by four key factors: Firstly, soil is now a net atmospheric CO₂ Carbon source rather than its sink; secondly, total soil respiration with seasonal fluxes being over twenty times greater than FF emissions (ratio 96:4%); thirdly, increases in CO₂ correlate more with forest clearance than with FF use; and, finally, while deforestation was unabated, 2020–2021 COVID shutdown of industry and transport reduced FF use by up to 26% with zero effect on rising CO₂. Such conclusions are evidently obvious if Land's Carbon stock fluxes are properly studied and fully reported.

Further evidence is UNEP (2025: figs. ES.2, 2.3) finding LUC as the greatest single contributor to excess CO₂ in 2024. Despite their misreporting LUC as net rather than cumulative, and excluding it from most totals, this proves subordination of FF use alone. A reversal flip of Soil as the major carbon sink to a net source, as suspected, is proven by recent studies reported herein, in particular latest ESSD Soil status by Hengl et al. (2026).

Final sections interlink the factors of Soil loss and maintenance, presenting a suite of examples (e.g. chemical Rothamsted and Organic Haughley) with cogent arguments for reducing meat and for restoration of more natural, Organic husbandry with vermi-composting, all based upon factual Science. Oversight of such options is because IPCC and other environmental bodies focus on Oceans or Atmosphere, often ignoring Soil. The few soil researchers tend to specialize rather than being broad ecologists and, as yet, no Soil Ecology Institute exists anywhere comparable to myriad Ocean/Aquatic or Atmosphere/Space facilities. Consequently, few data compilers have an affinity with Soil, fewer with Organics, which is reflected in basic misunderstanding of how Earth functions.

To make real progress, Science must retain its integrity, relevance and purposefulness. This is not controversial, being the essence of scientific research as everyone must agree. It is essential therefore that work is justified and worthy in the broadest possible context.

2.1 Soil Carbon and Climate Carbon

The current report considers Carbon cycles with carbon dioxide (CO₂) as the major greenhouse gas (GHG), others such as methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) are not of prime concern. However, it is noted that IPCC (2021: tab. 5.2) has natural methane emissions (in teragrams per year, or Tg/yr) mainly from Wetlands (~159 Tg/yr) but only 1 Tg/yr from Permafrost. Anthropogenic emissions are mainly from Agriculture (208 Tg/yr), half from cattle (109 Tg/yr) but only 31 Tg/yr from Rice. FF burning contributes 115 Tg/yr methane, or about half farming's. For nitrous oxide, Tian et al. (2024) report 40% increase from 1980–2020, due to chemical farming. Reports from Rothamsted experimental station in UK, as discussed later, showed organic fertilizers reduced methane (Powlson & Poulton 1998: fig. 8) but, when used in excess, tended to increase nitrous oxide (Clark et al. 2012).

Official references for Carbon and climate are the UN's periodic IPCC reports using data from annual Global Carbon Budget (GCB) published in ESSD Copernicus. The latest GCB (2025) is highly biased citing "ocean" 400 times, "atmosphere" 300, "soil" just 8, "organic" only once. IPCC suffers from similar bias, barely mentioning soil, as noted later.

Summary of latest IPCC (2021) AR6 report, drawing on GCB data, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Carbon budget with anthropogenic factors in puce. Note Land fluxes are of prime importance, but all are under-estimated so require major revision, as attempted herein. Comparatively, a lesser Ocean<->Atmosphere passive "gas exchange" and Ocean biosynthesis (GPP of 40 Gt C/yr and NPP of 20 Gt C/yr) have a small, near irrelevant effect on the global Carbon cycle. (Source - IPCC (2021: fig. 5.12). Online: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/figures/chapter-5/figure-5-12>).

At issue is IPCC focus for most CO₂ increase (+5.1 Gt C/yr) being from FF emissions (~10 Gt C/yr), yet this is a minor fraction (~2%) of annual Carbon cycle in terrestrial environment of 400–600 Gt C/yr. Their +5.1 Gt C/yr excess is mainly due to Soil failing as a net C sink (*vide infra*). Two major factual errors in IPCC's figure data are under-reporting of terrestrial Carbon stocks/fluxes, and the misrepresentation of Land Use Change (LUC).

2.1.1 Land Metrics Under-reported

Gross Primary Productivity (GPP) in Figure 1 is shown as Gross photosynthesis at (113 + 29 =) 142 Gt C/yr representing ~71 Gt C/yr Net PP (NPP) from the standard formulas of: $NPP \approx GPP - PR$ (Plant Respiration) $\approx SR$ (Soil Respiration/Decay plus Fire). Ideally, $GPP/2 = PR = NPP = SR$; in other words, an ecologically stable system has SR balanced by NPP.

Recently, Liang et al. (2023) found: “*The terrestrial gross flux is quantified to be 550 ± 60 PgC/year, falling in the range reported in the literature, 200–660 PgC/year.*” This may imply Land's NPP in a range of 100–330 Gt C/yr, supporting higher terrestrial NPP/SR of >220 Gt C/yr which was determined by Blakemore (2018b4) as evidenced from “*Barrow's 'bounce' flux, C/O isotopes, glomalin, and Rubisco*” (Blakemore 2024). Further support for higher NPP is from atom bomb isotopes in 1960s tests that suggest at least 80 Gt C/yr (Graven et al. 2024). Moreover, higher SR rates from newly revised Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC) totals in soil confirm higher terrestrial NPP, with this data presented below.

Koren et al. (2019: figs. 1, 4) also reported importance of terrestrial Carbon Cycle with Air-Leaf flux (F_{LA}) of -514 Gt C/yr, but their rather arbitrary starting point was: “*The magnitude of global GPP in our model is taken from SiBCASA and is -133 PgC/year for 2011.*” If terrestrial GPP were raised to more realistic levels, then their carbon cycle rates raise too.

IPCC's active carbon recycle rate on land (~142 Gt) plus passive Ocean “*gas exchange*” (~80 Gt) combined total of 222 Gt C/yr suggesting a residence time of all 870 Gt C in atmospheric CO₂ at (870/222 Gt =) 4 years, or more properly (870/142 =) 6 years. However, consideration of these recent studies indicates all atmospheric CO₂ is recycled, mainly via vegetation and soil, at two or three times this rate in just 1–2 years. Specifically, Liang et al. (2023) report a globally averaged turnover time, τ , of 1.5 ± 0.2 yrs and Blakemore (2024) gives similar time for recycling atmospheric CO₂ in just 2 years.

Terrestrial gross flux which IPCC has at ~142 Gt C/yr is thus 3–4 times underestimated.

Current GPP values are then about 440 Gt C/yr for Land and just 20–40 Gt C/yr for Ocean, as justified by Blakemore (2024), while Liang et al. (2023) say their derived global GPP “*is insensitive to the partitioning between the terrestrial and oceanic components*” which permits sinking their ocean GPP to a lower value. IPCC (2021: fig. 5.12) Ocean GPP is shown as 40 Gt C/yr indicating NPP of just 20 Gt C/yr that may be within bounds. Liang et al. (2023) carbon exchanges are not entirely related to GPP as they note that “*The oxygen isotopic variation of leaf and soil water is controlled by evapotranspiration, influenced by*

atmospheric relative humidity.” Nevertheless, they also advocate for upping estimates of land NPP, and for this to achieve 220 Gt C/yr, its GPP would be around 440 Gt C/yr which is less than their rate – on land alone – of 550 Gt C/yr. They say: “*terrestrial net ecosystem exchange (NEE) is better studied but gross primary production (GPP) processes (such as photosynthesis) comprising > 3/4 of the total carbon fluxes in the carbon cycling budget*”. This implies Land’s GPP is (550 x 0.75 =) 412 Gt C/yr, hence a modest 206 Gt C/yr NPP.

The summary data after Liang et al. (2023: tab. 2) in Table 1 show agreement across studies of 1–2 yr turnover time (τ) and GPP raised up to (290 ± 30 =) 320–412 Gt C/yr (to give terrestrial NPP up to 206 Gt C/yr?), but these are most likely underestimated and may be upped for terrain and other factors, as are revised and explained in more detail below.

Table 1. Carbon Recycle Rates, after Liang et al. (2023: tab. 2)

Sources Methods	Present Data based	Laing et al. O/C Isotopes	Welp et al. ENSO O/C	Beer et al. Eddy CO ₂	Hoffman et al. Dole effect
Recycle years (τ)	1.0 – 2.0	1.5 ± 0.2	0.9 – 1.7	-	-
τ (Northern)	-	1.2 ± 0.2	0.4 – 0.8	-	-
τ (Southern)	-	1.8 ± 0.2	2.6 – 5.0	-	-
GPP Gt C/yr	>440	>290 – 412	-	-	“292 ± 20”
GPP (Land)	440	>170 – 412	150 – 170	123 ± 8	>200?
GPP (Ocean)	(20 – 40)	(<90 – 120?)	-	-	(<91 passive?)
NPP (Land) Gt C/yr	220	>100 – 206?	75 – 85	62	>100?

2.1.2 IPCC’s Soil/Plant Respiration and Fire Budgets

IPPC’s Soil/Plant respiration and fire emissions data also appear rather contrived: “*The corresponding emissions by total respiration and fire are those required to match the net land flux, exclusive of net land-use change emissions which are accounted for separately.*” These LUC are stated to be: “*Estimated as residual from the mass balance budget of fossil fuel CO₂ emissions minus atmospheric CO₂ growth and the ocean CO₂ sink, the global net land CO₂ sink (including both land CO₂ sink and net land-use change emissions).*” In other words, LUC is not independently derived, it is the contrived balance of total FF emissions minus atmospheric CO₂ and a supposed Ocean Sink. No allowance is made for Land to be the major net source of CO₂ – which it is clearly shown to be in the current report and in earlier studies, e.g. see Blakemore (2024: fig. 9) also shown below.

IPPC do accept a terrestrial greening or fertilizer effect due to CO₂ rising – plus greater nitrogen deposition (from excess N fertilizers), warmer temperatures, and longer seasons also contribute – but all this appears more than offset by greater rates of soil loss. Concomitant with CO₂ and N excesses, increases in plant growth (NPP) in models are: “*global CO₂ fertilization effect on photosynthesis of 30% since 1900, or 47% for a doubling of C_a [Carbon in atmospheric CO₂] above the pre-industrial level*” (Haverd et al.

2020). Although, as just noted, this increase in NPP is overwhelmed by a “Red Queen effect” of higher net forest loss (-35%) and >50% topsoil erosion and/or poisoning due to bad agriculture causing inexorable CO₂ rise, as will be described in the following sections.

2.1.3 Terrain Upped for Soil to Full Depth

To adequately compare Soil to other Carbon cycle stores – such as above-ground Vegetation, the Atmosphere, or Ocean – full, rather than partial inventories are required. The issue of neglected terrain as discussed by Blakemore (2018b, 2024) argues for doubled land surface area in most cases. Currently, all calculations based upon an unrealistic mirror-flat Earth, are demonstrably underestimated. Terrain amplification is supported by models in Voigtländer et al. (2024: fig. 2) with up to 2–3 times area increase; although they need to overlay this and add to their coarser scale topographic increases.

Moreover, for convenience, USDA arbitrarily set a maximum depth of ~1 m (48”), or less, in reporting of SOC and other soil characteristics. Yet depth to bedrock averages 13.1 m (plus ~8 m in friable saprock adds up to ~21 m) with Siberian Permafrost recorded down to 1.64 km and mineral soils in USA to bedrock at 3.12 km, as detailed in Blakemore (2024). Greater depth is confirmed by Harper & Tibbett (2013) sampling to 38 m in WA, Australia, a recent soil depth study from Japan (Iwahashi 2025) reporting “*mean of 18 m*”, and Feber et al. (2026) surveying mean soil depth to bedrock (DtB) in USA at 26 m.

Harper & Tibbett (2013) found Australian soils deeper than 1 m had two to five times as much SOC as surficial samples suggest. This supported by Rolando et al. (2021: tab. 1) reporting 80% of total SOC at depth (i.e., x5) but showing 0–500 cm soil having x10 SOC compared to the top 0–30 cm. Surficial samples of <1 m are thus quite unrepresentative.

Unsaturated, living soil is naturally functional at depth to bedrock or to (variable) groundwater/water-table, this aerated zone called the Vadose. For saprock, Moreland et al. (2021) report appears to validly average 8 m depth and with up to 30% extra SOC/DOC.

Soil with full 21 m depth being ten to twenty times over standard 30 cm or 1–2 m samples, is realized as by far the greatest C store and C source, exceeding all trees, air and Ocean, albeit these incomparably measured as above-ground only, to full altitude or to full depth.

2.1.4 New Soil Respiration (SR) and “Hot” DOC (Dissolved Organic Carbon) Updates

Soil carbon from respiration (SR) is split between heterotrophic microbial breakdown (SRh) and autotrophic plant root respiration (SRa) with SRh:SRa ratio ca. 60:40%, confirming SRh has a larger share (Hashimoto et al. 2015, Jin et al. 2024, Zeng et al. 2025). Often an SRh:SR total ratio is used instead, also computing at ca. 0.6 or 60%. SR mutually balances Net Primary Productivity (NPP) that is Gross Productivity (GPP) less Plant Respiration (PR), with SR:NPP ca. 50:50 of GPP. Confounding difficulties arise as both root respiration (SRa) as part of PR and root exudates as part of NPP are often overlooked.

Ren & Cai (2025) proposed that Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC) constitutes the most active carbon pool in Soil and plays critical roles in soil carbon cycling, plant productivity, and global climate change. This labile fraction is a relatively minor proportion of total SOC but, because it is a predominant substrate for microbes, its contribution to global C cycling is disproportionate. They newly doubled calculations to give 13.47 Gt DOC for 0–30 cm soil depth. From this a new total to full depth and arguably with terrain, may be similarly doubled to 106 Gt DOC since a prior value in Blakemore (2024) was 52 Gt DOC. This included data from Guo et al. (2024) who estimated annual carbon release from DOC respiration alone of 27.98 or ~28 Gt C/yr which, they said, accounts for ~29% of soil microbial respiration (SRh) and was three times fossil fuel emissions (of ~9 Gt C/yr). If their ~28 Gt C/yr is truly 29% of SRh total, then total SRh is ~100 Gt C/yr and, if applicable globally (SRh being 29% of 60% or 17.4%), total SR is then around ~160 Gt C/yr. However, Guo et al. (2024: tab. 2) data were for 7.2 Gt DOC (0–30 cm) – about half of Ren & Cai's estimate of 13.47 Gt DOC – therefore atmospheric CO₂ released from DOC alone may be reasonably doubled too to (28 x 2 =) 56 Gt C/yr, and should this be 29% gives total SRh of ~193 Gt C/yr. Hence, if SRh is 60% of SR (or DOC is 17.4% of SR), total SR is ~322 Gt C/yr.

From foundation concept of SR:NPP as 50:50 of GPP, then GPP totals (322 x 2 =) 644 Gt C/yr (much above current values) that further implies CO₂ turnover of (880/644 =) 1.4 yrs.

This new SR value is three times Zeng et al.'s global SR value of 102.2 Gt C/yr, which requires 'official' NPP be raised (currently 70–80 Gt C/yr) to range 210–240 Gt C/yr, further justifying NPP of >220 Gt C/yr that also confirms isotopic indication of rapid CO₂ turnover.

Support for upping DOC for depth is from Wu et al. (2024) sampling to 3 m whence they determined that: “DOC in deep soil (>100 cm) accounted for 52.53–65.46% of the total soil stock; CO₂ emissions in deep soil (>100 cm) accounted for 12.9–57.4% of the total soil CO₂ emissions”. Shallow samples miss these non-trivial contributions. Heterotrophic respiration (SRh) from subsoil (~2 m) can be higher than in topsoil (Quartucci et al. 2025), albeit only the soil surface emissions and exchanges define total terrestrial gas fluxes.

Another evaluation by Sha et al. (2022) modelled and mapped microbial respiration (SRh, herein as 60% of SR) estimating SRh:NPP ratio of 0.73 or 73%; hence, their terrestrial NPP of 68 Gt C/yr in range 56–85 Gt C/yr corresponds to ~50 Gt C/yr SRh. Doubled for depth then terrain, raises SRh to ~200 and gives SR=NPP (at 73% or 60%) range 274–334 Gt C/yr.

Sierra et al. (2024) concluded that, overall, DOC transport and bioturbation are generally only of limited importance for subsoil SOC stocks, which are instead largely determined by the balance between root-derived inputs (NPP) and decomposition rates (SRh). They showed that despite the C stored in the soil at depth being 100s to 1,000s of years old, the C respired is relatively recent. New carbon entering soil recycles quickly by microbial activity with rapid transit times. They modelled a mean transit value at 1.3 years, which is similar to the turnover times of atmospheric CO₂ in soil noted above of about 1.4 years.

These authors note that most microbial activity in deep soils is in the Rhizosphere, as is expected, but also in earthworm burrow “hot spots”. Sierra et al. (2024) charted both residence time and carbon age, which merges with recalculations of ancient, isotope-depleted, carbon as 11–50% of total SOC at soil depths reported by Copard et al. (2025). Earlier, Moreland et al. (2021) reported co-mingling of ancient and recent soils to depth.

2.1.5 Soil SRa (photosynthetic root) and SRh (soil microbial) Respiration Ratio Redux

Related to DOC respiration in the previous section, three recent studies estimated for total soil respiration (SR) that the heterotrophic proportion has increased relative to the autotrophic. A contemporary global average SRh/SR ratio in Zeng et al. (2025) was of $61.30 \pm 0.54\%$ with a decadal rise of 0.13%. Alternatively, a study from Liu et al. (2025) had SRh:SR ratios of 0.54 in 1990 and 0.63 in 2014 (a rise of 17% in 24 years or $\sim 0.7\%$ per year trend). Earlier, Hashimoto et al. (2015) had SRh:SRa at 51:40 Gt C/yr, an SRh:SR ratio 56% (or 0.56) and global SR of 91 Gt C/yr (1965–2012) increasing at annual rate near 0.1 Gt C/yr (or 0.11%). Zeng et al. (2025) SRh growth rate was 2.3 times higher than for SRa (0.65 and 0.28, respectively) and, for their total SR of 102 Gt C/yr, 0.013% (or just 0.013 Gt C?) annual increase. Zeng et al. (2025: figs. S2, 5) showed SR (102 with 61 Gt C/yr SRh), contributed 18.1% to atmospheric CO₂ growth, while fossil fuel (FF) emissions were 22.9% (plus 59% “Uncertainty”). As all SR values are increased threefold herein, so may Zeng et al.’s SR contribution be raised to $\sim 40\%$ of excess CO₂ or about twice that of FFs.

SR data indicates that, despite the well-recorded increase in photosynthetic productivity (‘Global Greening’), the proportion of SOC decay is increasing yet more rapidly, thereby adding weight to the present argument that CO₂ excess is increasingly from LUC soil loss not just FFs. If an average of SR ranges above of 300 Gt C/yr is 60% SRh, then an $\sim 0.7\%$ annual increase in SRh is net 1.3 Gt C/yr contribution to the atmospheric CO₂ increase.

Ciais et al. (2025) concur with a declining Land Sink (or a soil deficit?) with gross 1.73 Gt C/yr loss and net Land CO₂ sink of just 0.44 ± 0.21 Gt C/yr, a difference of 1.3 Gt C/yr too. Most recently, Hengl et al. (2026) report SOC now with an ‘official’ net loss of 25 Gt SOC in 20 years (also about 1.25 Gt C/yr), as corrected and discussed in a subsequent section.

2.1.6 Plant Respiration (PR) Above- to Below-ground (PRa:PRb).

Soil respiration (SR) has SRa and SRh proportions better reconciled, but few consistent values exist for ratio of plant respiration (PR) above- to below-ground (PRa:PRb). Approximate values from Ming et al. (2023) in a specific instance (a cotton field in NW China) have PRa and PRb autotrophic respiration, accounting for 24% and 24% (total 48%) and SRh 52% of total SR+PR, suggesting 50:50 PRa:PRb ratio. Tang et al. (2019) had global SRa mean range of 48–54 Gt C/yr over 1980–2010 with an increasing trend, similar to but lower than SRh, of +0.03–0.1 Gt C/yr ($< 0.2\%$) reflecting the ‘Global Greening’ effect. Blakemore (2024) quoted ‘official’ global SR values up to 108 Gt C/yr that, reasonably doubled for neglected terrain, enter the bounds of ~ 220 Gt C/yr balancing total NPP.

Supporting this, a mean SRa in Tang et al. (2019) amounted to roughly 54 Gt C/yr, when this SRa (or PRb) is calculated as 50% of total plant respiration, giving a PR also of 108 Gt C/yr that, doubled for terrain (plus depth?), further supports global NPP of ~220 Gt C/yr.

In summary, the main uncertainty is in aligning SRa = PRb allocations, shown graphically:

GPP (100%) = (NPP + PR ~50:50%); PR (PRa + PRb ~25:25%) = SR (SRh + SRa ~30:20%).

NASA's simple global Carbon cycle has PR = SR = NPP, in Figure 2 with updated values.

NASA Global Carbon Cycle

Updated Values (Gt C or Gt C/yr)

Atmosphere - 870 Gt C

Photosynthesis 440 Gt C/yr

Plant Respiration 220 Gt C/yr

NPP (Litterfall) - 220 Gt C/yr

Soil Respiration - 220 Gt C/yr

Fossil Fuels - 10 Gt C/yr

Plants - 2,400 Gt C

Soil Organic C - 30,000 Gt C

LUC - >3.3 Gt C/yr?

[Ocean Uptake and
Ocean Loss are
77.6 and 79.5 Gt C/yr
from IPCC (2021)]

Copyright 2010 GLOBE Carbon Cycle Project, a collaborative project between the University of New Hampshire, Charles University and the GLOBE Program Office.
Data Sources: Adapted from Houghton, R.A. Balancing the Global Carbon Budget. Annu. Rev. Earth Planet. Sci. 007:353-313-347; updated emissions values are from the Global Carbon Project: Carbon Budget 2009.

Figure 2. NASA's Global Carbon Cycle with their 2019 values updated from present study. (Source - <https://airs.jpl.nasa.gov/resources/155/global-carbon-cycle/> 16th Jan., 2026).

2.1.7 Global Oxygen Cycle Related to Global Carbon Cycle

Planetary systems interlink with a directly balanced relationship between the global Carbon and Oxygen cycles. Corresponding to an increase in atmospheric CO₂, due to loss of topsoil, Land Use Change (LUC) and the burning of Fossil Fuels (FF), is a decline of O₂. Figure 3 summarized a recent study, modified from Huang et al. (2018: fig. 4).

NOTE: Claims Ocean produces >50% O₂ are false, truly 0.0001%, near zero.

Figure 3. Oxygen cycle counter-balances C cycle. False claims that the Ocean supplies 50–80% of oxygen in each breathe are clearly debunked. This figure omits massive oxygen drawdown from deteriorating soils and desertification. (Source Huang et al. 2018: fig. 4).

This Oxygen cycle model assumes most depletion is from FF but downplays contribution from LUC or topsoil erosion that may be the major cause, thus radical review is required. For example, the stoichiometric ratio of Land Production x 2.667 for O₂ from GPP and NPP CO₂ at 440 and 220 Gt C/yr amount to 1,173.5 and 586.7 Gt O₂ per year, respectively. Claims that Ocean produces >50% of atmospheric oxygen are unsubstantiated (truly 0.0001%). Minor Ocean O₂ outgassing is similar to its small, passive, net CO₂ exchange.

2.1.8 Permafrost (up to 1.65 km or Greater Depth)

IPCC's Permafrost value of 1,200 Gt C (ambiguous to inclusion of boreal peat) is a vast underestimation, here raised over seven-fold to 9,000 Gt C. This from 5,000 Gt C in Blakemore (2024) plus "subsea" upgrade by Strauss et al. (2024), raised five-fold from a previous estimate of 560 Gt C to 2,822 Gt C plus an extra 400 Gt C deep Permafrost. It is likely +25% glomalalin further increases these to >3,500 and 500 Gt C. Revision may thus total (5,000 + 4,000 =) 9,000 Gt, or terrestrial Permafrost alone (5,000 + 500 =) 5,500 Gt C.

Surprisingly, IPCC (2021) omitted an earlier citation of Shelef et al. (2017) who said: "SOC mass stored in perennally frozen hill toe deposits alone vary from few percents to more than double of current SOC estimates", giving a maximal uncertainty of >2,000 Gt C. Importantly, that study somewhat validates the rationale to double soil samples for both depth and terrain, and for use of sigmoid curves rather than linear for slope calculations. Recent and rapid thawing and erosion of Permafrost/peat adds considerable amounts of ancient carbon, also as depleted in isotopes as are FF emissions (e.g. Copard et al. 2025).

2.1.9 Peat (Reported up to 200 m or Likely near 300 m Depth)

IPCC AR6 (2021) does not provide a separate estimation of the world's Peat carbon. Typical values ranged from 200 to 600 Gt SOC, until Blakemore (2024) showed that proper inventory (without terrain factor for waterlogged bogs and mires) amounted to 3,000 Gt C and, if underlying lignite is included, as much as 6,000 Gt C. Slight support is provided by Widyastuti et al. (2025) reporting up to 1,344 Gt C (or 942 ± 312 Gt C) to 'full depth' although this study ignores Blakemore (2024) and, amongst other omissions, fails to mention glomalin. Peat thickness range in their database is just "0.02 - 12.06 m" whereas another report has twice or thrice this with: "*Peat-DBase's deepest measurement is 3 527 cm [35.3 m]*" or "*Peat-DBase's deepest measurement is 2223 cm [= 22.2 m]*" (Skye et al. 2025a, b). Admittedly far from complete in coverage, this latter resource has a total Peat estimate of only "327–373 Pg C" (Skye et al. 2025c). Conversely, Crézé et al. (2025) modelled Peat to total only 344 Gt C at 1 m depth. Yet many Peat depths in UK are already reported at 12 m or more (e.g. Crymlyn Bog in Wales, Ford Moss or Border Mires in England, Ardtalla Estate on Islay and parts of the Flow Country in Scotland). Holme Fen Post in Cambridgeshire, UK sunk to 7 m in 1848 now has 4 m exposed, and the author's personal experience is in turveries on Raheenmore bog in Co. Offaly, Ireland with depth up to 15 m (see O'Kelly 2008). Furthermore (no pun), tropical peats are up to 18 m (Ruwaimana et al. 2020), and inadequacy is manifest in peat/lignite depth extending to 200 m, ten times their reported maxima. The 1.3-million-year-old Tenaghi/Philippi bog in Greece has peat/lignite to 198 m, possibly 280 m (Pross et al. 2007). Deep Peat is important for profound influence on its bulk density (e.g. often 0.02 g/cm^3 at the surface to $>0.35 \text{ g/cm}^3$ in deeper layers), and total SOC stock at depth such that: "*The shallowest peat of 1.01 m stores 56.5 kg C/m² and the deepest (6.63 m) 524.8 kg C/m²*" (Fyfe et al. 2013), another near ten-fold difference. Additionally, that report also has up to 28% extra organic carbon (mean 13.5%) in some sub-peat soils due to adsorption of dissolved (DOC) leachates; this too adds to total depth. Submerged/sub-sea peat/lignite are additional. Whilst avoiding double-counting of peatlands, often complicated by overlap with Permafrost intergrades, Peat nevertheless remains a major store at ~3,000 Gt SOC.

2.1.10 Mineral Soil (that Extends to >3.1 km Depth)

For total Soil, IPCC's data source was partly Jackson et al. (2017) who had 3,270 Gt SOC >3 m, whereas IPCC total is lower at (1,200 Permafrost + 1,700 Soil =) 2,900 Gt C to 2 m. Lin et al. (2024) had a SOC summary of 1,873 Gt C (range 1,086–2,678) to just 1 m while a new estimate is 2,822 Gt SOC in the top metre, or a 45% increase (Crézé et al. 2025). Interestingly, this is almost exactly twice that claimed by French 4p1000.org (reviewed by Rothamsted's Poulton et al. 2018) as their starting point of a total global 1,417 Gt SOC they schemed to increase. However, since Rolando et al. (2021) found soil up to 5 m had on average five or ten times greater SOC, we may then arrive at a total at least (1,873 x 5 =) 9,365 Gt that is easily doubled again for combinations of glomalin (with reported range

of 4–52% He et al. 2020), full depth (of average up to 21 m), and terrain (doubling most soil results) to arrive at a new sum, from Lin et al.’s low data, to now total >18,000 Gt SOC.

This tends to endorse estimates in Blakemore (2024) for (5,500 Permafrost + 3,000 Peat + 10,000 Soil =) 18,500 Gt C. This is reported to full depth, as indeed are Atmosphere and Ocean inventories. Depth at least doubles IPCC’s total to 6,000 Gt and neglected terrain double this to 12,000 Gt C, plus some 20–30% glomalin would total >15,000 Gt SOC. This may be doubled again for neglected Asia C components such as Dissolved Organic and Soil Sediments as per Blakemore (2024: tab. 2) to >30,000 Gt SOC, as is stated in the Abstract.

Despite previous misrepresentations that Ocean is Earth’s greatest carbon store (viz. ~38,000 Gt C) this value is for mainly Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC), while the ocean Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC) is just 700–1,000 Gt. Soil, now known with >30,000 Gt SOC, has near 30 times more Organic Carbon in all its forms than are found in the Ocean.

2.1.11 Vegetation (with Tree Roots Down to >120 m Depth, Mycorrhizae Adding to this)

Vegetation biomass of 450 Gt C (range of seven estimates) IPCC has from Erb et al. (2018) which claims full stocks yet is ambiguous as they make no mention of ‘roots’ and have one statement “*assuming 20% belowground biomass for estimates of AGB [Above-ground biomass] only*”. Santoro et al. (2022) reported on “*above-ground carbon*” in plant biomass of 600 Gt but seemingly this is dry matter so actually just 300 Gt C. Other authors are explicit this is for above-ground carbon biomass, as discussed by Blakemore (2018b: fig. 11). For example, Crowther et al. (2019) had 560 Gt C “*Aboveground*” biomass carbon stocks, their values corrected by Blakemore (2019) as in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Adapted from Crowther et al. (2019: fig. 2C) with SOC at least ten times greater than above-ground biomass (i.e., ratio 10:1). Their sum total from SoilGrids data is ~4,595 Gt SOC carbon to just 2 m depth, here doubled for terrain/depth. Dotted line indicates potential extent of SOC loss or, conversely, scope for its full restoration in arid deserts, or other degraded areas. Source - <https://veop.wordpress.com/2020/06/12/volume-4/>.

Roots extend to 120 m but are routinely sieved out of samples to report separately. Blakemore (2024) notes handling and analysis miss 100–160% below-ground biomass. Global plant Shoot:Root ratios generally average around 50:50, e.g. 0.9 in Qi et al. (2019).

For “Vegetation” IPCC’s 450 Gt C may similarly be doubled for below ground roots and fungal symbionts to around 900 Gt C, also doubled again for terrain to about 1,800 Gt C. An upper vegetation value in Blakemore (2024) is 2,400 Gt C which agrees with the earlier full-depth value from data in Rodin et al. (1975) of 2,400 Gt dry mass (halved for carbon content but doubled again for terrain, etc. to give the same, 2,400 Gt C biomass total). Realizing Rodin et al. may refer to original biomass, terrain and doubled roots still apply.

2.1.12 Land Use Change (LUC) as Major Carbon Contributor is Underestimated by IPCC

An unsettling issue is that on page 699 of IPCC Report, directly above their figure 5.12 and table 5.1, cumulative LUC of about 240 Gt C (or strictly 240 ± 70) in total from 1750 is reported, yet their figure only shows -25 Gt C. This net LUC value compares to their total cumulative Fossil Fuel (FF) emissions shown as -445 Gt C in both table 5.1 and figure 5.12. If the vegetation LUC of 240 were properly presented in figure 5.12 this would be more than a third of the total anthropogenic contributions, i.e., 240 LUC vs. 445 FF. Nor is it clear why a LUC value from Erb et al. (2018) of 466 Gt C LUC just in Vegetation is excluded. That alone exceeds their cumulative FF emissions, albeit LUC loss has two components: Vegetation and Soil (SOC) loss. About half of original topsoil has been lost from combined effects of farming and deforestation, ultimately all adding to SOC loss.

IPCC (2021: pg. 688) defines net LUC: “*It consists of gross emissions (loss of biomass and soil carbon in clearing or logging, harvested product decay, emissions from peat drainage and burning, degradation) and gross removals (CO₂ uptake in natural vegetation regrowing after harvesting or agricultural abandonment, afforestation).*” Then on page 689 they present values of 116 Gt C soil carbon loss (from Sanderman et al. 2017) and for Vegetation they strangely have just 447 Gt C (from Erb et al.’s 466?) to total 563 Gt C. This is indicative only as there are likely overlaps in accounting of clearing and erosion of soils. However, LUC total from both sources are underestimations for reasons explained below.

A major error in IPCC’s data is this misreporting of Land Use Change (LUC) as just -25 Gt C, rather than -240 as in their table, or likely -563 Gt C as just noted. If human-induced clearing (LUC) loss of Land’s vegetation and soil erosion has halved stocks, as suggested, then their current IPCC values around 450 Gt C and 1,700 Gt SOC, assuming depletion by up to 50%, would presumably be -2,150 Gt C albeit mainly the surface topsoil is lost. It is also inconsistent for IPCC to present Ocean’s largely irrelevant inorganic carbon +173 Gt C increase as finite, but not to give all other fluxes, including Land’s gross Vegetation and Soil losses, regardless of how uncertain or difficult these are to calculate accurately.

Accepting that 50% of both Soil and Vegetation was lost due to human activity since the Neolithic era, most rapidly in recent crop/pasture intensifications, and while claiming LUC at -32% is underestimated four-fold, Winkler et al. (2021) fail to give a total of C loss.

Independently, Wedderburn-Bisshop (2023, 2024a, b) reported net cumulative LUC emissions of 734 Gt CO₂ and a gross cumulative LUC emission figure of 2,027 Gt CO₂ for 1750–2020. This equates to a total of approximately (2,027 Gt CO₂ x 0.27 =) 550 Gt C LUC.

In a more recent report, Wedderburn-Bisshop (2025) estimated about double, 1,000 Gt C LUC, but also noted cumulative LUC totals were conservative due to source data from Houghton & Castanho (2023) using net deforestation thereby excluding re-clearing and other underestimations of forest loss, perhaps four times greater in extent than previous assessments. Additionally, two other major reasons for his modest LUC are that the study was limited to 1750–2021, ignoring ~400 Gt C deforestation prior to 1750; and, secondly, carbon from farm-lit fires suppress forest regrowth, which is typically excluded but, if included, would double agricultural carbon emissions. This implies his estimates may be raised two to four times for these factors. Moreover, when terrain and deeper soil and all root losses are fully considered, many of these factors may be doubled again. Hence this newly reported cumulative LUC total is plausibly still only a half to a quarter complete. Thus, a best “guesstimate” high value ~2,000 Gt C total cumulative LUC may be modest.

In further support, combined Forest and Soil LUC losses in context are compared to FF emissions as presented in the following, mainly self-explanatory, figures (Figures 5, 6).

Figure 5. Atmospheric CO₂ levels compared to CO₂ FF emissions. Source - [https://skepticalscience.com/CO₂-emissions-correlation-with-CO₂-concentration.htm](https://skepticalscience.com/CO2-emissions-correlation-with-CO2-concentration.htm).

Figure 6. (A) Conventional IPCC with data from GCB (2024) and (B) Corrected CO₂ accounting. From Wedderburn-Bisshop (2023) - <https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/202310.1863/v1> .

2.1.13 Summary of IPCC Deficiencies and Corrections

All the IPCC (2021) terrestrial values are substantially underestimated with Gross photosynthesis (GPP) shown as just 142 Gt C/yr, now in the range of 440–550 Gt C/yr, or four times greater. For organic stocks listed as Permafrost, Vegetation and Soils (totalling 3,350 Gt C) these are now >32,400 Gt C or nearly ten time greater. Most concerning is their Land Use Change (LUC) uniquely reported as net values of 1.6 Gt C/yr and -25 Gt C total, whereas a cumulative total LUC is not shown, unlike for the Fossil fuels emission (of -445 Gt C). A good LUC total, if also cumulative, is similar with at least -450 Gt C and likely much higher, in the order of -1,000–2,000 Gt C which would be forty to eighty-times above that reported! Oceanic inorganic carbon is shown with +173 Gt C added, but anthropogenic changes of neither organic nor inorganic soil carbon are reported, ditto for Vegetation losses which are substantial (estimated up to -50% in the last few centuries).

Several issues regarding IPCC’s terrestrial underestimation are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Major Discrepancies or Deficiency Errors in IPCC Data

Factor	IPCC 2021	Latest value	Difference
Terrestrial GPP Gt C/yr	142	~450	3.2
Terrestrial NPP (GPP/2 =) Gt C/yr	71	~220	3.1
Soil organic C (SOC) Gt C	1,700	18,000	10.6
Permafrost (+ Peat?) Gt C	1,200	12,000	10.0
Total Soil Organic C Gt C	2,900	30,000	10.3
Vegetation Gt C	450	2,400	5.3
LUC Total Gt C (1750 to date)	-25	-240->500	9.6->20.0
Mean Error x Factor			6.3–8.9

Ocean biomass of 3 Gt C is just 0.1% vs. Land's >99%. Ocean's Gross productivity (GPP) is likely overestimated at 40 Gt C/yr to give 20 Gt C/yr NPP, both just one tenth of Land's.

An updated global carbon metrics graphic summary is Blakemore (2024: fig. 9) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Global carbon cycle compared to IPCC's with raised GPP and Land stocks; proportional net LUC losses of about ~20 Gt C/yr are double FF emissions of 9.4 Gt C/yr. Source Blakemore (2024: fig. 9 - https://www.mdpi.com/biomass/biomass-04-00070/article_deploy/html/images/biomass-04-00070-g009.png; also <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2020/01/16/solum-solace/>).

Comparing Figure 7 to Figure 1 of IPCC (2021: fig. 5.12), a value of ~9.4 Gt C/yr FF with a total of -445 Gt C FF emissions covers a period of about $(445/9.4) \approx 47$ years; total LUC emissions of -1,000 Gt C for 50 yrs is ~20 Gt C/yr concurring with my estimate. LUC values in Figure 7 are derived from -1.6 Gt C/yr plant loss from Houghton (2007: fig. 1), and Buringh (1984: tab. 3.8) who had "release of soil carbon to the atmosphere" of -4.6 Gt C/yr as a "Realistic estimate" mainly due to destruction and conversion of forests to crop or pasture land; these older references possibly when Science was less compromised. Doubled for terrain is $(1.6 + 4.6) \times 2 = 12.4$ Gt C/yr LUC. For Fire / "Combustion" IPCC (2001: fig. 3.1) had 4 Gt C/yr and IPCC (2019) had 2.2 Gt C/yr that, also doubled for terrain, ranges 4.4-8 Gt C/yr. Note that IPCC AR6 (2021) does not budget fire, while Buringh (1984) reported that "Approximately 50 per cent of all the forest trees cut down annually in the world are used as fuel"; his table 3.8 listed 0.75 Gt C loss of soil carbon from "Fuel wood, fire"; more thorough accounts give fire values combining gross vegetation/wood C loss.

Thus, from Figure 7, a sum for Land Use Change emissions (LUC, possibly overlapping with some other deficits?) is estimated at 12.4 Gt C/yr; another 4-8 Gt C/yr of litter/humus and vegetation is likely lost to peat/forest fires and stubble burning. This gives combined terrestrial emissions, about twice annual FF emissions (9.4 Gt C/yr), at around 16-20 Gt C/yr that complies within range of LUC annual emissions as cited above.

Bai et al. (2025) infer a similar rate: “if 1 % of the annual SOC fluctuates, the loss or gain would be 24 Gt C, which is more than the anthropogenic C release to the atmosphere”.

IPCC’s inadequacies and underreporting of Soil explain why so many climate models fail.

2.2 Deforestation (part of LUC) Correlates Closely with IPCC CO₂ Carbon Increase

Mo et al. (2023) reported: “So far, humans have removed almost half of Earth’s natural forests, and we continue to lose a further 0.9–2.3 Gt C each year.” Forest loss is mostly in the tropics with their farm products exported (<https://ourworldindata.org/deforestation>).

Approximately 50% of Earth’s habitable land is used for farming and most of this from clearing of the forests since the Neolithic (starting 10,000 years ago). Due to perpetual regrowth or replanting, a net loss is now reported as about one-third of forests gone since the last ice age succession, half of that loss occurring in the last century. The primary driver is agricultural crop expansion with grazing now the leading cause of deforestation.

A strong correlation exists between rate of deforestation, itself an index of accompanying soil organic carbon loss, and atmospheric CO₂ accumulation. This is shown in the following two graphs, a third conventional graph is CO₂ vs. FF emissions (Figures 8–10).

Figure 8. The forest area reduction from 52 to 42 million km² is about -20% net loss. Other reports have -30–50 % loss. (Source - <https://euanmearns.com/> Energy Matters website).

Figure 9. Forest loss. Source - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2022/07/13/kantan/>.

Figure 10. “Official” NOAA (<https://www.climate.gov/media/14596>) chart of Carbon dioxide (CO₂) and emissions from fossil fuels (FF) and industry, ignoring Land-use change (LUC) (cf. Figures 5, 6 and 8, 9). Source - <https://ourworldindata.org/CO2-emissions>.

The increased FF emissions, albeit relatively minor compared to natural land fluxes, seem to have been accommodated by land drawdown processes up to 1960s, then CO₂ accumulated. The rapid CO₂ rise matches several other phenomena as much as it does FF use, such as deforestation rates, nuclear tests, agrichemical uses and accompanying soil acidification with effects on nutrients in food. These relationships are complex, but proper comparison of total cumulative CO₂ is with total emissions – both of FF and LUC.

2.2.1 Current Status of Forests

FAO (2025: page xv) Global Forest Resources Assessment for forest biomass estimates carbon stock at 714 Gt C, or 172 tonnes per ha. Forty-six percent (nearly 50%) of the forest carbon stock is in soil (225 Gt SOC), 44% in living biomass (247 Gt C above-ground cf. Santoro et al. (2022) report of ~600 Gt dry mass mainly in forests; and supposedly just 66 Gt C below-ground in roots, etc., this likely underestimated), and 10% in litter (41 Gt C) or deadwood (30 Gt C). Brunner et al. (2013) had a higher forest soil component (based on “FAO 2005” data) at about 400 Gt C while noting that belowground biomass excludes fine roots less than 2mm diameter (and fungal hyphae) that are more often included in SOC

totals. All these forest values can presumably be doubled for terrain and some for full soil depth considerations. A probable reasonable sum is now likely more than double the FAO value of 714 Gt C, which would therefore total ca. 1,428 Gt C in all standing forest areas.

Estimates vary for deforestation with net -33–50% clearance following the Neolithic Revolution, or up to 1,428 Gt C lost if 50% of an initial 2,856 Gt C for the current 50% remainder as just noted. A significant fraction (~35%) of the world's forests loss is since 1750, and likely about 500 Gt C of this lost in the last century. Thus, a reasonable estimate is between 500–1,500 Gt total forest carbon lost to erosion or to the atmosphere due to LUC, albeit with some regrowth or other lower carbon conversion uses post-clearance.

Wildfires also destroy forests and 2024 was particularly bad with record events, causing up to 40% of total forest losses (<https://www.wri.org/insights/global-trends-forest-fires>).

Deforestation rates provide a proxy for loss of vegetation and soil erosion that together contribute much more to atmospheric CO₂ excess than do the cumulative FF emissions.

2.3 Soil Erosion (also LUC) Related to CO₂ (and Fossil Fuel Emissions)

WWF says: “*Half of the topsoil on the planet has been lost in the last 150 years*” (<https://www.worldwildlife.org/threats/soil-erosion-and-degradation>) and a recent study by Ganzenmüller et al. (2025) concluded humans have depleted terrestrial carbon stocks by a quarter. That paper estimated terrestrial carbon deficit to be 344 Gt SOC, equivalent they say to a 24% depletion and comparable to all fossil fuel emissions over the past 50 years. Their predominant cause is SOC loss driven by expansion of pasture (30%) and croplands (24%), plus forest management (23%). Working at 1 km scale, actual figures they present of global terrestrial deficits are -234 Gt C for Vegetation (just 0.24 root:shoot ratio!) and -344 Gt SOC that sums to -578 Gt C total loss. They misrepresent soil as just 30 cm deep and ignore terrain, so their LUC value may be at least doubled to -1,156 Gt C.

As noted above, IPCC claimed that since 1750 to date, LUC (or “LULUCF”) has only released 240 Gt of carbon through the clearing of forests and other ecosystems, with a significant portion of this loss coming from changes in soil carbon stocks and a reduction in Vegetation's ability to sequester carbon. A much higher value of cumulative carbon emissions caused by anthropogenic land cover change before 1850 were estimated at 325–357 Gt C (Kaplan et al. 2010). Simply doubling IPCC data for terrain gives cumulative LUC up to 500 Gt C in total to date, or likely closer to 1,000–2,000 Gt C as reported above.

In a natural setting, soil formation exceeds erosion as shown in the amount of ancient atmospheric carbon accumulated in terrestrial systems (>30,000 Gt C). However, current soil erosion is orders of magnitude above its natural formation due partly to increasing LUC effects, especially deforestation and the ubiquitous poisoning of soils overwhelming their ecological processes co-evolved over aeons. Pimentel (2006) says soil loss at 10 to 40 times its rate of renewal is a major global food security issue that Pimentel & Burgess

(2013) estimated as 75 Gt/yr loss of fertile topsoil. Whereas Borrelli et al. (2017) challenged this, modelling 35.9 Gt/yr of (dry) soil eroded in 2012, or about two times lower, because they assumed a “flat” Earth their value may be properly redoubled. Blakemore (2023) had rates of soil erosion ranging 2,000–20,000 tonnes per second and if SOC averaged 2.5% this would now sum ~680 Gt SOC displaced or lost. Ancient SOC when eroded is as deleted in isotopes as are FFs. A depleted isotope argument to justify the main role of FFs in excess CO₂ is then no longer a feasible reason (Copard et al. 2025).

It is generally estimated that formation of 1 cm of topsoil takes around 100 years or more, but rate of agricultural induced erosion is much greater, calculated to average nearly 1 cm surface loss each year (Zang et al. 2021). An example of excessive topsoil loss is in cultivated fields in parts of Australia that commonly range from 1 up to 50 t/ha/yr (https://www.dpi.nsw.gov.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0008/270881/saving-soil-complete.pdf). While organic farming preserves topsoil, transformative Permaculture aims to restore degraded or depleted soils in short timescales under prevailing climates.

For erosion rates, Lal (2006: fig. 3.2, tabs. 3.4–3.5) had local SOC loss as high as ~6 Gt C/yr with most (~70%) redistributed over the landscape or buried, ~20% lost to the atmosphere, with the remaining ~10% flowing into the Ocean via rivers. This is shown graphically in Figure 11. Along with massive coastal erosion, Ocean’s carbon budgets largely relate to rates of soil transportation (and hence eutrophication and/or poisoning).

Figure 11. Soil erosion with rates doubled (in red) to allow for terrain (although riverine to ocean transport is dependent upon the samples and methods used), updated from Lal (2006: fig. 3.2). Source - <https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/202212.0258/v2>.

Note that IPCC (2021: fig. 5.12) has natural and anthropogenic transfers of carbon from soils to freshwater systems significant at 2.4–5.1 Gt C/yr, and loss via outgassing from lakes, rivers and estuaries at 1.5 Gt C/yr. Their Ocean transport rate is around 0.8 Gt C/yr.

Dredging was traditionally used for fertilizing fields or paddy, but sediments now accumulate runoff toxins. Blakemore (2024) estimated sediments with ~2,500 Gt SeOC.

Owens (2020) provides a comprehensive summary of deposition rates and toxins in sediments with an interesting figure of Phosphate use and nucleotide peaks (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Synthetic Phosphate fertilizer use (as promoted by Rothamsted) increased five or six-fold since 1960s. Nucleotide fallout was from atom-bomb tests also 1950–1960s. Pharmaceuticals, heavy metals and biocides dates noted. Source – Owens (2020: fig. 8).

Despite increased biomass production due to N/P/CO₂ fertilization and lengthening growing seasons, there has been an overall net global decrease in global soil carbon stocks, hence a net release of CO₂ to the atmosphere according to Kopittke et al. (2024), albeit their values are underestimated. For cumulative loss of topsoil, a 1984 estimate was 538 Gt SOC lost, or 27% of prehistoric superficial soil carbon stocks (Buringh 1984). A later study had 136 Gt SOC loss to the atmosphere alone since 1750 (Dinahkran et al. 2014), another estimate was 108–188 Gt C since 1850 (Houghton 2010). This latter concluded: “From 1850 to 2000, land use and land-use change released an estimated 108–188 PgC to the atmosphere, or about 28–40% of total anthropogenic emissions of carbon (274 PgC from fossil fuels)”. Doubled for terrain, this latter is 216–376 with median near 300 Gt SOC loss that, notably, exceeds both FF use and IPCC’s current +279 Gt C net CO₂ increase. Such evidence in this section supports current main thesis argument.

Average erosion for the last 150 years is about -2 Gt SOC/yr, but rates have progressively increased. Houghton (2010) calculated: “The net flux from land use and land-use change over the recent period 1950–2005 is estimated to have ranged between 0.8 and 1.6 PgC yr⁻¹.” Doubled for terrain, this is 1.6–3.2 Gt C/yr (median -2.4 Gt C/yr). Topsoil erosion estimates gain little from soil depth, yet terrain doubling of net soil losses alone plausibly accounts for atmospheric CO₂ increases above any lesser Ocean or FF contributions.

However, the rate of -2.4 Gt C/yr SOC loss from soil erosion is an underestimation of cumulative LUC losses directly from SOC (including aboveground litter and rhizodeposition) and indirectly from Vegetation (including by fire) that if combined total about 1,000–2,000 Gt C. Much of this was in the last few decades but averaged over the last century would give between -10–20 Gt C/yr SOC loss. This implies that Soil

respiration (SR) exceeds annual NPP at about ~220 Gt C/yr, and, moreover, Vegetation loss plus Fires are neither balanced nor conserved by plant regrowth and/or reforestation.

2.4 New ESSD for SOC loss/Acidification that Causes Excess CO₂ and Destroys Soil Biota

While claiming just 11 Gt SOC loss (0–30 cm!), Hengl et al. (2026: tab. 3, fig. 16) actually tabulate twice this net loss as >25 Gt SOC in 1 m topsoil from 2000 to 2022, primarily driven by deforestation and reduced peatlands. This confirms soil is no longer a C sink. It is not too bold to conclude this new ESSD data of 25 Gt SOC loss could be at least doubled or likely quadrupled due to terrain (x2–4), proper sampling to full depth (viz. a global mean 21 m including saprock not just 1 m, so x2→5), glomalin (+4–52%), DOC, and several other factors. Furthermore, soil data from Russia, with 12.5% of habitable (i.e., soil bearing) land and 20% SOC, is lacking as from India, China, Kazakhstan, etc. They “*also miss especially some peatlands in the tropics*”. This is very important because if their 25 Gt SOC loss is merely quadrupled to 100 Gt SOC, this loss mainly to the atmosphere (perhaps partly to aquatic systems?) represents about 50 ppm atmospheric CO₂ increase (conversion 2.13 Gt C = 1 ppm CO₂). Thus, SOC loss alone, irrespective of FF emissions, would account for almost all the approximately 48 ppm atmospheric increase between 2000 and 2022, based upon data from NOAA and other scientific organizations. These organizations (e.g. WMO) also report fossil fuel (FF) emissions for the 2000–2022 period, at 45% of all CO₂ emitted since the Industrial Revolution, sum to 193–225 Gt C (just equal to Land’s annual NPP!). A ready conclusion is that while soil via vegetation has grown to absorb much excess FF carbon, now, due to poor management, a net C loss or deficit from topsoil alone surely represents most atmospheric CO₂ excess.

Uncertainties are that Hengl et al. provide a total of 1,037 Gt SOC in the top 1 m which is more than doubled to 2,822 Gt SOC in an estimate by Crz et al. (2025). Most concerning, if -25 Gt SOC loss (or -1.25 Gt C/yr) in just the top metre is amplified for full depth and extended to region excluded from their calculation, then a net soil loss to depth is more likely ~125–250 Gt C in 20 years (or 6–12 Gt C/yr), rewriting climate models.

Contrary to this, Bilir et al. (2025) models maintain that “*Terrestrial ecosystems annually absorb ~30% of anthropogenic C emissions*” and appear to imply an increasing trend in the recent 20 years. Yet their almost impenetrably complex analysis has simplistic starting points such as initial (“*dead*”!) soil carbon of just 1,417 Gt C total which is completely inadequate compared to best estimates of 8,580 Gt, or now >30,000 Gt SOC.

Hengl et al. (2026) also newly show uniform (LUC) acidification seemingly around -1.25 pH which, if so, represents a staggering 1,680% shift in H⁺ ions in just 20 years. This supports my previous estimates that soil is the greatest store and source of atmospheric CO₂ as well as being the biotic Realm most subjected to massive biodiversity loss. If real, Hengl et al.’s catastrophic soil acidification they call “*a slight trend toward acidification*”, may represent crossing of a threshold for survivability of keystone taxa like Bacteria or

earthworms in an irreversible and negative-feedback downward spiral. Their most stark (LUC) changes in the 22-year period are shown as up to -5 pH points in “*Grassland*” and “*Cropland rainfed*” representing 50% of habitable land that are essential for food thus our survival (Figure 13). Non-trivial, this -5 pH change is ten million % in relative acidification.

Figure 13. Soil acidification is a non-trivial condition, greatly endangering soils globally.

Soil pH reduction by -1.25 in 20 years supersedes Meng et al. (2019: fig. 5) simulation data of -0.24 pH in 1–14 years at 20 sites, presumably intensifying all related soil disbenefits (viz. -19.1% fine roots, -14.7% soil respiration, -9.6–12.1% microbial biomass, toxic +Al).

Synergy of SOC humus loss, soil acidification, plus toxic agrichemical pollution are irresistible forces portending collapse of Land ecosystems we entirely rely on to continue to thrive; as do all other vital soil microbes, fungi, worms, insects, birds, and mammals.

2.5. Summary of Soil and Carbon/Climate

In summary, there is an undeniable increase in FF emissions, but also a similar increase in rate of deforestation (with accompanying release of ancient Soil SOC). A 30% “*global greening*” effect has taken up much of the extra CO₂ as a natural ecological process. That there is excess CO₂ is due almost entirely to the loss of topsoil (SOC) that reduces the plant growth potential. SOC loss is mainly due to mismanagement when agriculture is treated as a chemical process rather than as proper ecosystems. Simple remedy is thus in restoration of natural, Organic farming. Agriculture and food production are the major causes of forest destruction, of peat loss, and the associated soil erosion with the major driver of increasingly rapid erosion of these essential life-support systems being excess meat production. The next section considers the disbenefits of extravagant meat-eating.

3.1 Soil and Food Security

Defining the scope of the issue, total Land Area requires correction for topographic terrain and microrelief rugosity that, in a combination of overlays, may quadruple Land's surface from 15 Gha to >64 Gha for a Land:Ocean ratio of 64:36% (Blakemore 2018b). Although Land area apportioning increases, its relative % proportions remain (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Conventional Land and agricultural, true surface area now x2–4 for terrain (cf. Blakemore 2018b: fig. 4). Urban areas are still about 1% but Water bodies, being level, are hence reduced to <1.5%. Ocean fisheries & aquaculture supply just 1% of human food, 6% of total protein. Source - <https://ourworldindata.org/global-land-for-agriculture>.

About half habitable land is farmed, over 80% of this is for livestock that, depending upon choice of diet, provides a relatively small proportion of food (17% calories, 38% protein). Thus, most human food is already plant-based (83% calories, 62% protein) with relatively efficient land use. Footnoted is Ocean's food contribution at <2% as: "fish and seafood from aquaculture production which uses land for feed. If wild fish catch is included, animal products would provide 18% of calories and 40% of protein." So, proportionally 99% of our total food is from the Soil, only about 1% from Ocean fisheries. Pimentel (2006) estimate was of just 0.3% of human food from aquatic sources, 99.7% from soil.

Because nearly all calculations of terrestrial productivity, biomass or carbon stocks, and rates of erosion, etc. are based upon planimetrically flat models, these manifestly underestimate (Blakemore 2018b, 2024). Correction for terrain may make models more representative of the true situation. Overall area difference was shown to be about quadruple at finer scale overlays as applicable for solar radiation or microbial biodiversity, but a more conservative doubling is most appropriate for most other data. Although criticized in an uninvited Comment on the original paper, as noted in the Appendix, a study by Voigtländer et al. (2024) supports Blakemore (2018b) in that intricacies of terrain were shown to double or triple surface areas, depending on scales.

In addition to terrain, the established Leaf-Area Index (LAI) increases the biotic surface area for photosynthesis and gas-exchanges, plus there is superficial biocrust and

cryptogams (lichens and moss, etc.). Mean, single side LAI is $4.5 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$ from Asner et al. (2003) which multiplied by topographic soil-bearing land is ($\sim 50 \text{ Gha} \times 4.5 =$) 230 Gha. Whitman et al. (1998: 6580) assumed forest LAI of $10 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$ (unstated whether single-sided or not), either case further ups Land's reactive surface areas to approach 500 Gha.

Comparably Ocean's flat insolation/gas-exchange area is just 36 Gha (or 7% of this total). Corollary is with amount of the photosynthetic energy enzyme Rubisco recently reported on Land at about 1.4 Gt (98%) vs. 0.03 Gt (2%) in marine environments (Blakemore 2024). Phytomass in the world's oceans of 0.08 Gt C is 30,000 times smaller than that on Land. Moreover, Land's Phytomenon (e.g. Cyanobacteria, unicellular Chlorophyta), are more abundant and productive than all Ocean's phototropic Phytoplankton (Blakemore 2024).

An obvious underestimation example, therefore, is for terrestrial GPP/NPP where the isotope and other indicators show global productivity much higher than that extrapolated from per unit area productivity. To correct this requires doubling, either of all these local data, or of Land's total surface area (as applied to baseline data herein). Confirmation that manifestly hilly land and bumpy soil area should be considered as a factor in models is also confirmed since a mirror-flat Earth has yet to be convincingly proven at any scale.

Roughly 14% of land surface is shown as desert or degraded, this often instigated or exacerbated by fire (e.g. firestick farming, slash and burn, firewood), or cultivation and overgrazing from pre-industrial times to date; another 10% area is covered in ice. Of the potentially habitable land remaining, about 50% has been cleared and converted for agriculture with the majority laid down as pasture. Land degradation due to this is estimated at between 20–40% (median 30%) of total according to the UN Land Outlook Report (2021) whose lead author stated: “*Modern agriculture has altered the face of the planet, more than any other human activity. We need to urgently rethink our global food systems, which are responsible for 80% of deforestation, 70% of freshwater use and the single greatest cause of terrestrial biodiversity loss.*” The latest 2024 UN Desert Report (https://www.unccd.int/sites/default/files/2024-12/aridity_report.pdf) claims drylands are rapidly expanding so they “*cover more than 40 per cent of global land (excluding Antarctica).*” The report also cogently argues for more sustainable agriculture systems.

Ultimately the best and only soil loss and excess CO_2 remedy is drawdown via Organics.

3.2 Imperative to End Agrichemical Farming – A Farewell to Farms?

Chemical agriculture, also marketed as “*conventional*”, that gradually expanding from the 1900s and was more widely implemented since 1960s, has now mostly run its course. Synthetic ‘Superphosphate’ (contaminated with Cd) was extracted from fossilized coprolites by Rothamsted institutions in 1840s. Synthetic nitrates were a by-product of the munitions industry needing disposal (for profit) following the 1914-1918 war. Biocides were developed at the same time as poison gasses for trench warfare, their use as pesticides gradually expanded following WW2 in the 1940s and following the

agricultural inspired Green Revolution of the 1960s. The following two charts (Figures 15, 16) show extent of the synthetic chemical expansion compared to other farm metrics.

Figure 15. Fertilizer and biocide use increased dramatically in 1960s (cf. Figure 12). Source - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2018/05/27/wormageddon-destruction-in-our-soils/>.

D. Agricultural production

Land use change and rapid land use intensification have supported the increasing production of food, feed and fibre. Since 1961, the total production of food (cereal crops) has increased by 240% (until 2017) because of land area expansion and increasing yields. Fibre production (cotton) increased by 162% (until 2013).

CHANGE in % rel. to 1961

- ① Inorganic N fertiliser use
- ② Cereal yields
- ③ Irrigation water volume
- ④ Total number of ruminant livestock

Figure 16. Triple yields (+200%) correlate more with doubled irrigation (100%) than x9 synthetic N fertilizer use (and excess biocides). Source - IPCC (2019: fig. SPM.1D).

Much of this increased crop yield has been used for stock-feed. As is shown below, yield is an illusion (or delusion?) at the true cost of the nutritional quality and safety of our food, also incurring intolerable destruction and irresponsible extinction in the Natural world.

Due especially to observable declines in flying insects and birds as a consequence of the increasingly toxic environment, are issues of poor soil/food health and soil erosion. Thus, it is becoming increasingly obvious that chemical farming has largely failed and must be curtailed. What increases in crop yields there have been require greater chemical inputs to maintain, and these are accompanied by massive soil erosion and toxic poisoning of the environment and our food, now also depleted in nutrients. Due to overuse, several pest plants and insects are resistant to biocides requiring yet more toxic mixes, and similarly intensive stock rearing has promoted antimicrobial resistance. Other issues are irresponsible and uncontrollable spread of GMOs with their ability to reproduce and spread, more pernicious than toxic chemical pollution that may, eventually, dissipate.

Symptomatic of critical insect collapse, a recent European study reported a -99.3% orb-weaving spider decline in recent years (Nyffeler & Bonte 2020). At such extinction rates, the biodiversity heritage remaining to be passed on to future generations will be severely depleted. This is reminiscent of the message in Rachel Carson's (1963) "*Silent Spring*".

Should the agrichemical industry repay its environmental and health costs, profits would nullify. Thus, rationale for chemicals now makes neither ecological nor economic sense.

Organic methods preserve Nature, offering safe, healthy and abundant foods whilst also conserving humus and earthworms in soils that may have 25% greater soil moisture than their conventional/chemical neighbours, which is equivalent to extra rainfall or less irrigation. This before deliberate moisture retention tactics are employed, such as Yeoman's Keyline system as advocated by Permaculture (Mollison 1988). Permaculture offers Design for Nature systems aiming to achieve self-sustaining food and energy having minimum input (work or chemicals), less waste, and zero pollution. It too focuses mostly on the foundational aspects of preserving, restoring or rebuilding healthy topsoils. Furthermore, the best solution to CO₂ emissions is simply to reduce excessive red-meat.

3.3 Imperative to Reduce Red Meat – 'Chews Wisely'

Forest clearing is mainly for agriculture and mostly directed towards meat production. The carbon footprints of different food systems and diets are commonplace, advocating for reduction of excessive meat eating. Consensus data show the most wasteful use of land is for sheep (and goats) which are responsible for destruction and extension of degraded lands into marginal states. Plants are unable to regrow, nor soils restore due to over-grazing. Beef is directly responsible for most clear-felling of pristine, climax forests.

The following three figures (Figures 17–19) show land use with itemized components of carbon costs across the whole food supply chain (mainly LUC or on-farm emissions).

Land use per 100 grams of protein

Land use is measured in meters squared (m²) per 100 grams of protein across various food products.

Our World in Data

+ Add food

Source: Poore, J., & Nemecek, T. (2018). Additional calculations by Our World in Data. OurWorldInData.org/environmental-impacts-of-food • CC BY

Figure 17. Protein costs; note that dairy is much less demanding of land resources.

Source - <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/land-use-protein-poore>.

Food: greenhouse gas emissions across the supply chain

Our World in Data

Note: Greenhouse gas emissions are given as global average values based on data across 38,700 commercially viable farms in 119 countries. Data source: Poore and Nemecek (2018). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. Science. Images sourced from the Noun Project. OurWorldInData.org - Research and data to make progress against the world's largest problems. Licensed under CC BY by the author Hannah Ritchie.

Figure 18. Carbon cost is mainly LUC and on farm; transportation (in red) is a minor proportion of total. Source - <https://ourworldindata.org/food-choice-vs-eating-local>; see also - <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/food-emissions-supply-chain> that shows when food losses are included, nearly 100 kg CO₂e is required to produce 1 kg of beef.

What are the carbon costs of different foods?

Total carbon costs is the sum of greenhouse gas emissions from food production, plus the opportunity costs of land. Using land for agriculture – either crops or pasture – prevents natural vegetation such as forests, or wild grasslands from growing on that land.

Source: Schmidinger, K., & Stehfest, E. (2012). Including CO₂ implications of land occupation in LCAs – method and example for livestock products. OurWorldinData.org – Research and data to make progress against the world's largest problems. Licensed under CC-BY by the author Hannah Ritchie.

Figure 19. Carbon. Specific sources matter, e.g. Brazil beef is ten time more costly than Dutch or Irish beef. Source - <https://ourworldindata.org/carbon-opportunity-costs-food>.

These charts demonstrate that excessive meat is most destructive and is particularly damaging in places like Brazil where rainforests are cleared. As an alternative, OWiD calculated that: “If the world adopted a plant-based diet, we would reduce global agricultural land use from 4 to 1 billion hectares” as presented in the following Figure 20.

Global land use for agriculture across different diets

Global agricultural land use is given for cropland and pasture for grazing livestock assuming everyone in the world adopted a given diet. This is based on reference diets that meet calorie and protein nutritional requirements.

Data Source: Joseph Poore & Thomas Nemecek (2018). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. Science. OurWorldinData.org – Research and data to make progress against the world's largest problems. Licensed under CC-BY by the author Hannah Ritchie.

Figure 20. Refined diet choices with moderate dairy herds grazing on pastures also being providers of manure fertilizers. Source - <https://ourworldindata.org/land-use-diets>.

Of the diet options, as with most other human endeavours, moderation and compromise are often best policies. Thus, the completely Vegan diet is ill-advised as well as being unhealthy unless the food is 100% organic (due to critical nutrient depletion issue as well as carcinogenic and other pollutants from overuse of toxic chemicals on all other farms).

If environmental issues of common concern are insufficient incentives, possibly personal health penalties of over-indulging in meat may help people choose their best diet. The next two charts are trends of meat consumption versus cancer rates (Figures 21, 22).

Figure 21. Meat consumption from OWiD. Source - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2020/05/27/realms-of-the-soil/>.

Figure 22. Cancer rates from OWiD. Source - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2020/05/27/realms-of-the-soil/>.

Australians are the most overindulgent in meat (120 kg/yr per person or about twice the average human bodyweight in some States) and cancer prone. These charts show that excess meat consumption is not essential (compare US to China's 60 kg/y or India's 5 kg/yr), rather it is a cultural issue (compare US to Japan that is as affluent but has a more mixed seafood diet). A reasonable compromise aims for 50% meat reduction to <60 kg/yr.

Similar goals to reduce, or at least halve, cancer cases may benefit from less red-meat. As genetics propensity for cancer may vary little between countries, ill-health as revealed by national data is assumed to relate either to external environmental issues or to diet and lifestyle choices. Medical costs from poor diet or unhealthy food are penalties in addition to the huge environmental costs of chemical farming responsible for most meat.

3.4.1 Imperative to Restore Soils with 100% Organic Farming/Permaculture

A summary of progress and benefits of Organic is by Gomiero et al. (2011). Badgley et al. (2007) estimated average Organic yield ratio for all crop types at global level as 1.32 (i.e. organic would produce 132% of chemical yields). While Smith et al. (2018) estimated just 0.62, or 64% of that under 'conventional' was possible with 100% Organic in the UK. There are flaws in both of these reviews, such as assuming the same levels of excessive N fertilizer are required from legumes or omitting N-fixing in composts. Howard (1940) reported as much as 25% additional N is fixed in compost (although N-P-K are trivial). Accepting that current levels of red-meat excess are unrealistic, a strategy report by Muller et al. (2017) shows options to feed 10 billion humans using Organic farming alone. Sanders et al. (2025) meta-analysis confirms many Organic benefits, as were just noted.

Offering solutions, there yet remain many problems with the current state of Organic husbandry and farming. The impression is given that Organic competes with Conventional/Chemical, but it only occupies about 2% of farmlands with over half of this in arid or marginal lands in Australia where the massive properties are too large to spray chemicals anyway. The total area of "*organic and cultural land*" in Australia is about 35 million ha out of about 372 million ha farmland. Just one company, Hewitt, operates over 2.2 million ha of cattle and sheep stations with a single property, Narwietooma in the desert NW of Alice Springs in the Northern Territory (NT), spanning 1.1 million ha with a herd of 35,000 stock or >30 ha/head. It may be questioned how such operations can be classed Organic if not prioritizing preservation or restoration of healthy soils. In comparison, Sikkim in India has become the first wholly organic State with its 75,000 ha of farmland (10% of area) now farmed organically. This is just half the size of the NT farm.

Thus, to imply Organic, truly only 1% of total farmed area, competes with Conventional Chemical farming is quite misleading. Currently it is a marginal fringe activity at best. Organic regulatory bodies are often also remiss or negligent to allow hydroponics (quite detached from soil), as are false organic premium produce claims from chemical or "Regen" farms and other lapses such as unregulated "Organic" imports. Although some

practitioners are well intentioned in trying to adopt relatively recent promotion of Regeneration, or Regen, this is already kidnapped or co-opted by agrichemical industry.

3.4.2 The Contentious Issue of “Regen” vs Real Organic

The term Regenerative or “Regen” as a synonym for reviving Organic farming was first proposed by the pioneer Organic Rodale Institute in the 1980s - <https://web.archive.org/web/20250917214317/https://rodaleinstitute.org/why-organic/organic-basics/regenerative-organic-agriculture/>. Widely promoted in recent years it has simultaneously been corrupted from its Organic origins, mainly by corporate interests or by researchers who only know chemical agronomy. True Organic farming has a clear definition to avoid synthetic poisons, sewage, or GMOs instead striving for healthy soils, plants, food and humans. Regen is open for interpretation with ill-defined and easily exploitable boundaries. This is summarized in Rodale Institute’s chart (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Rodale’s practices of Chemical vs. Regen vs. True Organic for promotion of food, farming and human health (reminiscent of the ‘600 Cheshire Doctors’ aims from 1939 as reported on in the Appendix herein). Source Rodale’s THE POWER of the PLATE - <https://web.archive.org/web/20240406000719/https://forainitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/Rodale-Institute-The-Power-of-the-Plate-The-Case-for-Regenerative-Organic-Agriculture-in-Improving-Human-Health.pdf> (from Rodale Institute, 2020).

Just as “Agroecology” has been diluted in its original meaning by inclusion of agrichemicals and GMOs, the difference is now eroded between Conventional/chemical farming and the kidnapped term “Regen”. However well-meaning the practitioners hope to be, they are misled by industry incentives (i.e., marketing, advertising hype, profit motive and lack of any accountability for pollution nor responsibility for human or animal

ill-health). Only clearly stated Organic practices avoid all synthetic chemicals, GMOs, sewage sludge and the routine dousing or injection of livestock with antibiotics or synthetic growth hormones. Permaculture goes further and, unlike many industries or institutes with profit motives, has stated Ethics. These are three reasonable ideals of Earth Care, People Care, and Fair Share. One step further is to reduce cruelty of red-meat.

That the term Regen has been “kidnapped” and greenwashed by chemical industry is shown in support by profit-motivated agrichemical giants that actively oppose true Organic farming and are often the direct or indirect sponsors and controllers of Academic research publications: e.g. Bayer/Monsanto, the promoter of GMO genetically modified crops, and biocides (especially glyphosate/Roundup)- <https://web.archive.org/web/20250925225938/https://www.bayer.com/en/agriculture/regenerativeag> ; or Syngenta/ChemChina manufacturer of toxic Paraquat and Atrazine - <https://web.archive.org/web/20251004010213/https://www.syngentagroup.com/regenerative-agriculture#can-regenerative-agriculture-feed-the-world> .

The definition and implementation of Organic farming need to be clarified not corrupted; also proper, unbiased, Scientific scrutiny is required for confirmation of its cost-benefits. Ecological comparisons should compare chemical, in all its forms, to 100% real Organic. Degraded land can indeed be regenerated, by implementing genuine Organic husbandry.

4.1 Examples of Organic Yields and SOC (Rothamsted and Haughley experiments)

An existing system cannot be criticized without the provision of practical alternatives. In this section the compelling and multiple benefits of Organic farming – in terms of yield, carbon sequestration and biodiversity preservation – are demonstrated as being entirely achievable without the penalties of pollution with destruction of the soil and environment. Examples are from Rothamsted and from Organic Haughley experiment, details of which may be found elsewhere. Evidence of farming in this area of UK since prehistoric times (6,000 yrs), and during the Roman occupation of Britain (2,000 yrs), had sustained these soils for millennia prior to the experiments being overlain. At the plot, field, or whole farm scale, each have compared Organic vs. Chemical regimes as follows.

4.2 Rothamsted’s Broadbalk Wheat Experiment from 1839

Broadbalk field at Rothamsted Research in the UK is the world's longest-running scientific field experiment starting in 1839. Since 1843 it has continuously grown winter wheat to test effects of different fertilizers and manures. The experiment's purpose is to study crop yield and soil chemistry, and it has been modified over time to remain relevant. Control plots include both an original organic manure fertilizer, and zero or “Nil” fertilizer.

Details of this trial and results of several comparisons of organic vs. chemical/conventional in global settings, including Haughley, Broadbalk and other Rothamsted experiments are provided in Blakemore (2018: tab. 17). Overall, yields of

crops or milk were on average +17.8% in favour of Organic production where benefits of soil health were also manifest. An arial shot of Rothamsted’s Broadbalk is in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Broadbalk with lush Farm-Yard Manure strips on the right (Plots 1, 2.1, 2.2), Plot 3 is Nil Fertilizer and Plot 4 has no Nitrogen. Wilderness is at the top West of the field. Source - www.era.rothamsted.ac.uk/metadata/rbk1/Broadbalk_handout_2024.pdf .

4.2.1 Broadbalk Yields Equivalent (Despite Only Partial Organic Practices)

Figure 25 shown latest data from Broadbalk presented with key yield findings.

Figure 25. - Broadbalk yields of winter wheat 1852-2022. Fertilizers are “organic” Farm-Yard Manure (FYM from non-Organic stockyards) or chemical N-P-K. FYM at 35 t fresh material per hectare is equivalent to approximately 3.2 t organic C/ha/year (ca. 240 kg N, 45 kg P, 350 kg K). Source - <https://doi.org/10.23637/rbk1/meanWYields1852-2022-03>.

Post crop rotation restoration in 1968, the yields of FYM plots were also greater than any of the chemical treatments for both oats (20%) and maize (60%) as well as potatoes and beans being substantially higher (e.g., https://www.rothamsted.ac.uk/sites/default/files/national-capability/long-term-experiments/Web_LTE%20Guidebook_2019%20Final2.pdf tab. 2; <https://www.era.rothamsted.ac.uk/eradoc/article/ResReport1982p2-5-44>; <https://www.era.rothamsted.ac.uk/eradoc/OCR/YieldBook1984-9-13>).

Broadbalk's adjacent Hoosfield Spring Barley plots yield 50% higher in FYM treatments compared to N-P-K (https://www.rothamsted.ac.uk/sites/default/files/national-capability/long-term-experiments/Web_LTE%20Guidebook_2019%20Final2.pdf fig. 7).

Yield data at Rothamsted prove organic FYM (Farm-Yard Manure) plots as consistently equivalent, or above, synthetic chemical N-P-K plots. Moreover in 1968 the re-introduction of crop rotations (a standard organic practice in the 1840s) doubled the test crop yields. Often these data are misleadingly published only that chemical N-P-K greatly increased yields over Nil fertilizer (an impractical control concept). As well as ignoring the FYM yields, the destructive and detrimental effects of chemical fertilizers and biocides compared to any Organic practices are regularly downplayed or ignored in some reports.

As with other chemical interventions, in order to maintain yields at Broadbalk, the fertilizers rates have had to continually increase. Nitrogen applications range from 48, 96, 144, 192, 240, up to 288 kg N/ha/yr. That the experiment has run its course is also shown by re-introduction of the traditional Rotation standards to replace the failed monoculture.

4.2.2 Broadbalk Soil Organic Carbon (SOC = Humus) -60% Lower

Soil organic carbon (SOC) with organic FYM compared to artificial N-P-K was depleted from ca. 85 to 35 tC/ha or -60% in their most recent data (Figure 26). Often this data is misreported as an increase in N-P-K plots over Nil fertilizer plots from 25 to 35 tC/ha or +40%; with the FYM plots (+240% in their form of reckoning) being completely ignored.

Including adjustments for increased organic C at depth on FYM plots since 1844, 1885 and 1968. Continuous wheat sections only, since 1968. Start values in 1843, 1884 and 1967 were estimated (.....). Decreases between 1914 and 1936 are due to the introduction of regular fallowing in 1926. FYM was not applied in fallow years (- - -). Updated from Powlson et al, 2012.

Figure 26. Soil carbon from the fertilizer trial plots from Rothamsted Research (2021). Source: Broadbalk soil organic carbon content 1843-2015, *Electronic Rothamsted Archive, Rothamsted Research* - <https://doi.org/10.23637/KeyRefOABKsoc-02>.

SOC shows a very interesting story as from the starting point in 1884 this field had been “run down” through four previous years, starting in 1839, of crop rotations without fertilizers. Fertilizer used prior to this would have been organic compost materials; thus, the original carbon level would have been higher, likely around 50-60 Gt C. This is important as the chemical N-P-K plots have retained the depleted soil carbon levels, around 30 Gt C, barely above the zero-fertilizer plot. Perhaps not unsurprisingly, the FYM plots that best preserve the original soil conditions had higher earthworms or, rather, the N-P-K plots were depleted in both carbon and earthworms (by up to 90% as noted below).

Often just these depleted N-P-K plots that are compared in their proportions of artificial fertilizers that are recommended in the most recent agrichemical advocacy papers, e.g., Tang et al. (2025) claimed “plots receiving nitrogen and phosphorus fertilisers contained up to 28% more soil organic carbon than those left unfertilised”. Rothamsted also claim: “Across dozens of long-term fertilisation trials worldwide, nitrogen and phosphorus were associated with average soil carbon increases of 21% and 13%, respectively.” (<https://www.rothamsted.ac.uk/news/fertiliser-boosts-soils-ability-lock-away-carbon-0>). Truly all these plots were SOC depleted when more properly compared to FYM plots.

A similar situation occurs when claims of no-till carbon and earthworms are said to be enhanced when, in actual reality, the relative values may be raised slightly, but from massively depleted proper values. This was clearly demonstrated at Haughley where the soil carbon and earthworms were both reduced by around 80% in chemical compared to Organic (or a compromise Organic with chemical fields equating to FYM+N-P-K plots at Rothamsted). Thus 20% remaining, if doubled, still only represents 40% of the original.

Misplaced logic also applies to carbon subsidies that exclude Organic farms on the false argument that they are already sequestering carbon to its limit. If such subsidies were seriously applied, these would reward existing or transitioning Organic farmers, valuing their experience in offering working models for reformed chemical farmers to emulate.

4.2.3 Broadbalk Rewilding Woodland (Wilderness) as an Upper Control and Exemplar

Nature’s ability to revive when abandoned is shown at Broadbalk in a particularly useful demonstration of an additional section which is rarely reported on, that of the Wilderness section divided into forest or stubble. This was fenced in 1881 and set aside to regrow.

Compared to the best FYM plots on Broadbalk, the carbon content is naturally higher in the rewilded Wilderness section, that all had similar starting C t/ha levels (Figure 27).

Figure 27. Broadbalk’s rewilding carbon sequestration above- and superficially below-ground. Source – <https://www.era.rothamsted.ac.uk/dataset/rbk1w/01-BKWoc>.

The soil carbon content at 23 cm depth starts about the same level as other depleted plots but gradually increased to more than double at >100 t/ha organic C. These are the most modest totals as the soil to the full depth of the roots may hold much greater carbon, as indeed the roots and their mycorrhizae may too. Often root C is about the same as the above-ground vegetation. Thus, in total inventory the Broadbalk Wilderness may have about double the 450 value to above 900 t/ha organic C which would represent the amount of carbon potentially lost from these soils on initial forest clearing (that is classed as Land Use Change or LUC), shown reduced to just 30-90 t/ha organic C. Conversely, this clearly demonstrates potential – and achievable – SOC restoration rates.

Abandoned or set-aside farmland, if fenced to prevent stock over-grazing, may naturally regrow to its ecological optimum. While replanting is part of Permaculture (with saplings or seed-balls), another common practice is to simply set up perches and let the bird droppings work naturally and for free, as indeed this Wilderness plot regrew naturally.

4.2.4 Broadbalk Grain Nutrient Depletions

It is timely here to introduce perhaps the most alarming evidence of collapse of chemical farming with the widespread and catastrophic loss of nutrients, minerals and vitamins in their products. The example from Rothamstead is also from Broadbalk trial (Figure 28).

Broadbalk experiment

Changes in yield, harvest index, grain Zn and Fe concentrations

Fan et al, J Trace Elements Medicine Biology 22 (2008) 315–324.

Figure 28. Mineral decline in wheat for three Broadbalk plots (Nil control, plot 3; N-P-K, plot 7; and FYM, plot 2.2 or 2b listed as "22"), open circles and black lines for FYM. The decline started after 1968. Harvest index is (grain/(grain+straw)) yield efficiency which suggests grain yield dilution is not the cause as Control plot grain also declined. This report claims CO₂ fertilization effect is minor, just 5% of decline, compared to crop varieties. Source - www.rothamsted.ac.uk/article/fact-or-fake-news-our-food-becoming-less-nutritious.

Data for several other Broadbalk plots and other minerals (viz. Cu, Mg, Ca, K, S and P) were tested and found with similar declines but were not reported. Harvest Index (HI) is the grain to straw ratio; hence, the lower yielding control plots have low grain yield but same HI when "dwarf" seeds were introduced in 1968, this cancelled yield dilution as being a causal factor. In FYM grain, minerals were increasing since 1840 but collapsed at the same date as the others, albeit their declines were not as pronounced. Unfortunately, what effect adding N-P-K to the FYM in plot 2.1 since 1968 had on grains from that plot compared to FYM only in plot 2.2 are unreported. Note that the 2000s data in the chart show Iron (Fe) in FYM plot at 30 and N-P-K plot at 20 mg/kg, a -33% or a +50% difference.

The graphs document critical nutrient declines, widespread across produce and regions, commencing in the 1960s and have progressively worsened. Causes or combination of factors for its onset are unclear, but the effects may contribute to corresponding declines in plant, insect, animal and human health. This key subject requires greater investigation.

As early as 2002, Loladze (2002) suggested rising CO₂ affected plant nutrients, an argument supported in later publications (e.g. Loladze 2014, Ebi et al. 2021) (Figure 29).

Figure 29. Carbohydrate/protein C in plants increase with elevated CO₂ associated with decline in minerals ion “ionome” that form the basis of nutrition. Source Lolazde (2014).

Causes of nutrient decline from the 1960s at Rothamsted, Fan et al. (2008) attributed *only* to introduction of chemically-dependant dwarf wheat varieties developed for the Green Revolution. This is immediately questioned as a theory as similar and synchronous declines are reported for other crops, including fruits and vegetables without “dwarf varieties”, from many other countries and climatic regions of the world (e.g. Davis 2009) suggesting some other overriding cause. A follow-up study by Mariem et al. (2020) compared similar declines as in Broadbalk grain with those from around the world, concluding the cause is due to the new varieties plus increased CO₂ and/or temperatures. What the Rothamsted reports fail to evaluate is that “Herbicides” were also introduced along with the new wheat dwarf varieties. Their report says this is MCPA (e.g. ref - <https://croplifefoundation.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2012/07/2-broadbalk.pdf>) but there is evidence that the controversial glyphosate biocide (as in Roundup) has been used along with many other chemicals (<https://www.era.rothamsted.ac.uk/eradoc/OCR/YieldBook1990-10-14>). Fungicides were also used and this alone, as with glyphosate that is patented as an anti-microbial and chelating agent, may be responsible for nutrient declines in plants if it interferes with the mycorrhizal associations that are largely responsible for plants’ ability to take up minerals from the soil. The ‘Global Greening’ as a confounding contender is noted below.

If partly true, the dwarf seed argument for nutrient depletion adds yet more reason for Organic produce. These “dwarf” varieties higher grain yields cost is in greatly reduced straw stock (this a valuable cover mulch or compost ingredient). Rothamstead states “*New seed was bought each year up to 1963. From 1963 saved seed from the previous*

Broadbalk crop (bulked from several plots and well mixed) was sown.” This is reminiscent of infamous contractual obligation of Monsanto’s “Roundup Ready” clients forced to buy new seed annually. This is contrary to common-sense, best practice, and the heritage of organic farmers passed down over millennia to keep and replant or share heirloom seed with neighbours. Seed saving and sharing is also routinely practiced on Organic farms to this day. Most crops we now entirely rely upon were domesticated in precisely this way.

An interesting follow up to nutrient declines by Adams et al. (2024) disputed the dwarf-variety argument showing it was subordinate the production environment, although they did concede “*compared to ancestral and historic wheats, modern wheats also have been shown to have smaller and slower-growing root systems, which may decrease plant access to soil minerals.*” Pertinent to this, Blakemore (1981, 2000, 2018a) found Haughley Organic wheat roots significantly increased +10.8%. Later, Hirte et al. (2021) show organic with (+40%) and root-shoot ratios (+60%) compared to conventional wheat.

Regarding the onset in 1968 of nutrient decline in the Broadbalk wheat grain, Rothamsted have had to increase fertilizer rates from 144, up to 240 or then to 288 kg N/ha to maintain yields. Thus, excess fertilizer may be a partial cause of nutrient declines, not just seed varieties and as they claim. Other possible causes of food nutrient declines are excess CO₂ (with possible effects of nuclear testing changing carbon isotope ratios?), soil acidification and N deposition from acid rain, or other drifting biocides where use of these expanded greatly from the 1960s. Supporting evidence for the causes and remedies for this nutrient decline are, for example, by Garvin et al. (2006) and Thomas (2007) from USA and more widespread by Myer et al. (2017) or Bhadwaj et al. (2024). A recent review comparing the nutrients in Organic foods is by Rahmen et al. (2024).

That nutrient decline occurs in natives (e.g. goldenrod *Solidago* spp.) as well as crops further diminishes the varieties argument, supporting CO₂ enrichment (Ziska et al. 2016).

The possible contribution of acidification to the nutrient decline from combined effects of N deposition and rising CO₂ are difficult to determine as the situation on Rothamsted is complicated by liming or marling required to maintain a balanced pH on some chemical fields after their initial rapid and critical pH drop. The broader global issue of critical soil acidification will be addressed in more detail below. Another contender in some reports is warming aspects of climate change, however the following chart argues against this, at Rothamsted at least, as rather than in the 1960s when nutrients declined, the increased temperature trend started later, after 1980s, currently at +2 °C (Figure 30).

Figure 30. Rothamsted temperature trend shows a sharp +2°C rise in 30 years or +23% (compared to surface Ocean rise +0.50°C since 1982). Source - Blakemore (2018: fig. 11).

Noting the importance of this issue, a subsequent study (Ebi et al. 2021: fig. 1) found that, for rice at least, the particular varieties had very different responses to increased CO₂ levels, which partly supports Rothamsted’s claim that that varieties are partly to account for nutrient depletion, but this by itself does not debunk being related to CO₂ levels. Possibly some other factors are important to account for the seemingly sudden onset of nutrient depletion (e.g., agrichemicals, although glyphosate was only introduced after 1974; or, as noted, atmospheric atomic bomb tests that spiked in the early 1960s).

A review by Bhardwaj et al. (2022) concluded nutrient declines in food since the 1960s are due to combinations of “*agronomic issues associated with the shift from natural farming to chemical farming*” and to the rise in atmospheric CO₂. In summary conclusion these authors also advocate Organic restoration, as does the current report, of “*soil biodiversity and fertility: those are main causes behind the decline in nutritional density*”. At the moment the cause, or likely combinations of causes, of the widespread and critical food nutrient declines remain unclear. A summary with citations of the food nutrient issues is in a 2023 report - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2023/08/29/critical-decline-of-minerals-nutrients-in-agrichemical-vs-100-organic-foods/>. The report by Bhardwaj et al. (2022) cited studies of organic food with more vitamins and minerals (e.g. Vitamin C +51%, Fe and Mg +41-69%) compared to conventional/chemical foods.

On whether Organic food escaped nutrient decline was investigated in a comprehensive review (Holden 2001) which concluded (on pages 30, 63) that mineral content of Organic produce may, on balance, be the same or higher than chemical but the toxic residues much lower, as would be expected. This further supports the restoration of Organic foods.

Moreover, Vigar et al. (2019) state that *“Likely to be of more importance than compositional differences between the two, is what organic foods do not contain. Organic foods have been shown to have lower levels of toxic metabolites, including heavy metals such as cadmium, and synthetic fertilizer and pesticide residues. Consumption of organic foods may also reduce exposure to antibiotic-resistant bacteria”* They reported significant positive health outcomes in longitudinal studies where increased Organic intake was associated with reduced incidence of infertility, birth defects, allergic sensitisation, otitis media (ear infection), pre-eclampsia, metabolic syndrome, high BMI, and non-Hodgkin lymphoma (a type of cancer). Again, this endorses the health benefits.

Mayer et al. (2022) recently reviewed Organic food with higher mineral nutrients and dry matter (higher moisture may associate with supposed yield hikes). They concluded: *“For a range of reasons, agroecological farming should be supported in the context the global climate emergency and loss of biodiversity. The limited evidence that compares nutritional value of organic versus conventionally grown F&Vs [Fruit & Vegetables] adds an extra reason to switch from industrial to agroecological farming.”*

More investigation is needed on underlying causes and remedies of food health issues, as with Rodale’s “POWER of the PLATE” or the 600 Cheshire Doctors Report in Appendix.

4.2.5 Broadbalk’s Catastrophic Biodiversity Collapse

As well as soil carbon and crop nutrient declines, there have been large loss of biodiversity. Blakemore (2018a) reports on Rothamsted Insect Survey (RIS) that plotted a decline over a 30-year period (1973–2002) in one of four UK sites noting rapid agricultural intensification from the 1950s caused a collapse before monitoring commenced in the 1970s, a characteristic of broader and critical extinction issues on a global scale.

However, this issue is more chronic and with greater obfuscation as the collapse of insects and other soil fauna was already reported on from Rothamsted in the 1920s – about one Century ago or about 80 years after its inception – in the surveys by Morris (1922, 1927). Morris (1922: 303) had Rothamsted’s Broadbalk earthworm counts of about one million in manured arable plots and 0.46 million per acre in Nil “control” (equivalent to 250 m⁻² and 113 m⁻², or a decline of about –55%). On other fields the insects and invertebrates were reduced by 90% and earthworms were depleted too, being completely annihilated (i.e., reduced to zero) in the Ammonium or Superphosphate plots (Figure 31).

Fig. 3. Distribution in depth of the more important groups in the various plots.

Rothamstead data on earthworms (Oligochaeta) from Morris (1927: fig 3 - <https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.18345/page/n493/mode/2up>).

Figure 31. Status of invertebrates and earthworms (Oligochaeta). From Morris (1927).

Morris's study showed soil-dwelling Oligochaeta (earthworms) thrived with highest counts in the FYM "Dung" plots and these 'organic' plots had no yield penalties, as noted. Later, microbial biomass of FYM plots was about twice that of the plots given either N-P-K or no fertilisers (Jenkinson & Powlson 1976), and similar to results are found elsewhere.

4.2.6 Rothamsted N Deposition and Soil Acidification Reflects a Global Issue

Continued soil acidification is a serious degradation issue affecting half of arable soils, posing a significant threat to food security and exacerbating Green House Gasses (GHG) (Xu et al. 2025). As noted, Hengl et al. (2026: fig. 16) show recent soil acidification average about -1.25 pH ranging up to -5 pH points. At Rothamsted it was recognized early on that adding Superphosphate and Ammonium salts causes extreme soil acidity. For example, Crowther (1925), also a Century ago, reported on this while noting: "*Farmyard manure, on the other hand, has produced a significant reduction in acidity, equal to about +0.5 in the pH value. Farmyard manure is generally regarded as a moderator of extreme conditions, and has been spoken of as a "buffer."*" This conclusion omitted from subsequent Rothamsted reports that track rates of acidification (1856–2000) (Figure 32).

Fig. 1. The pH of soil samples taken at various times from (a) the surface (0–23 cm) horizon of the Park Grass Experiment. ● Plot 3, unmanured; ▲ Plot 9, ammonium-N₂ P K Na Mg; ■ Plot 14, nitrate-N₂ P K Na Mg; (b) three horizons from the Geescroft Wilderness: □, 0–23 cm; ○, 23–46 cm; △, 46–69 cm.

Figure 32. Geescroft Wilderness pH declined 3 points. From Johnston et al. (1986: fig 1).

Johnston et al. (1986: tab. 2) determined that >70% of most recent acidification was due to deposition (mainly from Ammonium-N ions in acid rain and dry sulphate gas or dust). Goulding et al. (1998), nearly 30 years ago, concluded that artificial N deposition from the air was a significant problem, changing ecosystems through eutrophication and acidification. Significantly, they reported: “Our research has shown acidification resulting from atmospheric deposition, including N, under woodland as well as grassland. Soil pH has decreased from 7 to 4 or less in 110 yr, mobilizing aluminium and toxic metals.” This extreme >3 pH points change is an acidification increase of 100,000%! Comparatively, the Ocean Acidification of pH -0.1 in 200 years as claimed at just 30% is a distraction. Nitrogen deposition to winter cereals at Rothamsted were stated as c. 45 kg N/ ha/yr and deposition to woodland c. 100 kg N/ha/yr or more. The authors make the remarkable statement that: “Such an amount of ‘free’ N would greatly benefit organic and other low input farming systems.” Yet most Organic growers would balk at this as they try to avoid all synthetic pollution that acidifies soil and stimulates microbes to consume the humus.

This N benefit argument seems negated by the Zero N control flat-lining at Broadbalk, getting no apparent extra yield from a massive increase in N deposition since the 1960s.

Blake et al. (1999: tab. 1) give further details of acidification at Rothamsted, and globally, noting that to maintain soils at their present pH, or allow some recovery, requires deposition values to be restricted by returning to pre-industrial emissions of <5 kg/ha/yr each of S and N. They also document an already “irreversible degradation of soil quality”.

In a long-term 140-year hay/pasture study at Palace Leas in UK, Standen (1974) reported highest yields, pH, SOC, and worms with organic FYM; some chemical plots had zero earthworms. The pH differed by up to 2 points but both lime and fertilizer had been added.

Another example of pH change on a relatively remote Australian site has a native pasture control being acidified mainly from acid rain compared to the P fertilizer plots (Figure 33)

Figure 33. Declines of about -1.5 pH in Australia; upper curve is for untreated and natural pasture plots, lower curve for adjacent P treatment plots. Source - Schefe et al. (2015).

Schefe et al. (2015) found P treated soil is more acidic over time, and in some cases, exchangeable Aluminium (Al) concentrations approached levels impacting production. Al toxicity is expressed by the stunting of plant roots that limits their proper functioning.

Globally, soil acidification from excess N and S (and C) deposition in acid rain is a major, but mostly ignored, issue that requires more scrutiny. Soil acidification is catastrophic to soil biota and also to micronutrient availability plus negative effects of Aluminium release. Earthworms and microbes fail to survive or thrive in soil pH values below 4 or 5.

4.2.7 Broadbalk Soil Bulk Density (BD) (Required for Total Carbon Calculation)

Reflecting that the whole experimental field had been allowed to “run down” for four years before testing, BD in 23 cm topsoil stayed compacted in NPK plots from 1840s but lessened from 1.25 to 1.10 g/cm³ (-12.5% or +13.6%) in the FYM plots. Wilderness is lower yet at about 0.9 g/cm³. This decompaction is primarily due to higher humus carbon content and aeration actions of extra earthworm activities. Total SOC calculation requires BD data (sourced from - <https://www.era.rothamsted.ac.uk/info/rbk1/soilphys>).

4.2.8 Broadbalk Soil Moisture -33% Reduction

Data for soil moisture from Clark et al. (2012: tab. 1) show 32% in FYM (plot 2.2) and mean of 26% for NPK plots (a point reduction of -16%) which was about the same for the Nil plot. Wilderness woodland was much higher at 41% soil moisture. Another report had 16% in Nil plots (presumably similar to NPK) and 24% in FYM plots, which is +50% more or, rather, -33% lower (<https://files.core.ac.uk/download/pdf/162100858.pdf>: Table III).

4.2.9 Broadbalk's Fungi Collapse by -80%, and Rhizosphere Bacterial by -40%

The glomalin proxy for fungi showed generally low activity but five-fold greater levels in both FYM plots and Woodland compared to NPK plots, or with an -80% decline (Young et al. 2020: fig. 2B). Nitrifying bacterial counts ranged 0–18,000/g of dry soil, the maximum number being found in the Broadbalk FYM plot (Soriano & Walker 1973). Rhizosphere bacterial taxonomic units (OTUs) differed in the FYM plot (2.2) compared to N-P-K plots from around 1,880 to as low as 1,100 OTUs, a -40% reduction (Kavamura et al. 2018). This confirms microbes as greatly enhanced in Organic fields in general (e.g. Lori et al. 2017).

4.2.10 Broadbalk's Earthworms Collapse by -94%

Sizemur et al. (2017), as in Blakemore (2018: tab. 12), found earthworms depleted from 400/m² and 109 g/m² in FYM to 70/m² and 6 g/m² in N-P-K plots or with a catastrophic -94.4% loss. This confirms earlier studies by Morris's (1922, 1927) showing agrichemicals devastate earthworms, this alone heralded demise of chemical farming from inception.

4.3 Rothamsted Compared to Organic Haughley

The Haughley Experiment was established in 1930s by Lady Eve Balfour in the UK to test and compare the results of Organic and non-organic methods on a whole farm scale with a design approved by Rothamsted and yields independently assessed by Cambridge University. Three sections of the same farm were operated independently as either wholly Organic with all produce recycled and excess (crops or milk) sold off; or a Stockless section using prevailing practices of chemical farming. A third section was Mixed – a compromise of the two. Details are provided by Blakemore (1981, 2000, 2018a). In summary, crops were as high or higher in the organic sections (by +7.7%) and the soil had 25% extra moisture and about double both the carbon content and earthworms. Or, more correctly, the chemical fields had -6% lower crop or milk yields, -29% lower moisture, -56% SOC humus, and -44% lower earthworm abundance with -48% less vermi-biomass.

Near equivalency of yields, but also depletions of carbon and earthworms, as reported from Rothamsted, e.g. in their Broadbalk trials with FYM compared to N-P-K, closely resembled Haughley's Mixed section with soil as poor as in the chemical Stockless fields.

The conclusion from all the above data is that the Rothamsted experiments proved from their earliest days that retaining organic fertilizers maintains yields, biota and soil health while chemical fertilizers (and other synthetic biocides) are inordinately destructive not just on the actual farm, but to the whole of the wider ecosystems at a global scale. Further information on the success and failures on Rothamsted are available here - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2023/11/11/roth-rebu/>. Finally, despite all evidence from their trials, a 2009 Rothamsted article dismissed Organic as a viable option (unless meat consumption is reduced) <https://research.wur.nl/en/publications/can-organic-farming-feed-the-world-a->

[contribution-to-the-debate-o/](#) . Another 2021 study argued the contrary: viz. that Europe could feed itself with Organic farming alone - <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2021.05.008>. Other countries too could be self-sufficient if Organic and Permaculture principals were followed and chemicals reduced.

4.4 To Plough, or Not to Plow?

The benefits of ploughing and harrowing on Organic farms need to be balanced with alternative methods of weed control and seed bed preparation. A recent trend for conservation agriculture with reduced tillage or direct-drill (sowing seeds behind narrow tines that rip the soil) assumes that cultivation harms soil and that spraying a farm with glyphosate or some other biocide is benign. The inappropriate comparison within and between chemical farms or fields alone, show these techniques as damaging compared to overall outcomes on Organic farms. Moreover, Organic farming has many options for weed control (e.g. cover crops, mulching, rotation to reduce seed banks, and manual, flame, or mechanical methods) other than ploughing as appropriate. Certain “weeds” are tolerated as green-mulch or as host plants for the life- stages of pest-predatory insects.

It should also be noted that the Rothamsted Broadbalk plots were fallowed in the 1920s which involved ploughing and harrowing several times, yet the slightly depressed carbon levels soon recovered. This also pertained to the Organic Haughley fields that were traditionally ploughed before sowing which seemingly had almost negligible effect on the carbon and earthworm counts, these both being significantly higher than in the chemical fields. The conclusion is that cultivation is not necessarily detrimental and is a valid weed control method itself preferable to blanket herbicide spray for zero-till and direct-drill. This is endorsed in a 2025 report - <https://sustainablefoodtrust.org/news-views/its-not-the-plough-but-the-how/> and in a reduced tillage benefits study (Apostolakis et al. 2025).

As disingenuous as reporting chemical yield increases or carbon storage compared to zero fertilizer crops, or just the relative amounts of chemical applied, is the comparison of cultivation effects. Both Rothamsted and Haughley results show that cultivation does not decrease SOC nor earthworms in the long term, rather it is the overriding issue of inorganic fertilizer and toxic chemicals applied that deplete both of these. Ploughing (or plowing), as an established practice for controlling weeds and preparing seedbeds, is not as deleterious as portrayed. However, a common practice of spraying glyphosate in lieu of cultivation does have profound consequences in contamination and toxicity to fungi, earthworms and farmworkers as well as the general public consuming the food produce.

4.5 Other Innovative Interventions CCS/BECCS vs. Soil/Earthworm CCS (S/ECCS)

So far in this report the beneficial aspects of Organic are reported in humus (= carbon capture and sequestration) as well as interlinked effect of an earthworm abundance. Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) or Biomass Energy and CCS (BECCS) at their most ambitious claims are relatively trivial compared to other practical and proven (i.e.,

natural) carbon removal options. Relative and proportional importance is documented in Project Drawdown and shown in carbon cycle data (Blakemore 2024: fig. 14) (Figure 34).

Figure 34. Global Carbon Cycle from Blakemore (2024: fig. 14) with relative proportion of anticipated BECCS/CCS shown as the tiny black dot with claims of 0.0105 Gt C/yr. Note that soil respiration/erosion/burning (in brown) at ~220 Gt C/yr is x22 FF emissions of just 10 Gt C/yr and that the excess CO₂ of 5 Gt C/yr is now due entirely to collapse of Soil sink.

Referencing that Organic farms are only about 1% of total and that biomass of earthworms (and other soil biota) declines are around >80% within the majority of agricultural compared to wholly Organic farms, as reported by Blakemore (2018a), translates to large losses. A relatively simple solution is to preserve earthworms and to attempt to restore the depleted populations to their optima. Several earthworm species remove concentrated atmospheric CO₂ from their burrows via their calciferous glands, secreting “inorganic” calcium carbonates (CaCO₃), conservatively estimated at about 1 Gt C/yr as earthworm calcite as noted below. Restoration of the 80% depleted populations would presumably increase secretions five-fold, at least in farmland and some woodland biomes. If, for example, this represents 20–25% of habitable land that is earthworm depleted, then the extra cast carbon stored would be about +1 Gt C/yr. Such options are reported as Soil/Earthworms CCS, or S/ECCS here - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2019/11/11/earthworm-cast-carbon-storage-eccs/>. Further work is needed to determine merits and tangible benefits of more S/ECCS.

Production of earthworm derived CaCO_3 is possibly much higher, as it is reported up to 261 kg C/ha/year in habitats of some species (Versteegh et al. 2014). Taking agricultural land at 10 Gha (already doubled for terrain) would translate as 2.6 Gt C/yr; to include forests presumably doubles this rate. Other estimates are of up to 2.24 t C/ha/yr which, for 10 Gha farmland, would be about 20 Gt C/yr extracted from atmospheric CO_2 and potentially stabilised for >300,000 years (Lampkin et al. 2011, Versteegh et al. 2013).

Tellingly, the most modest 1 Gt C/yr earthworm calcite is more than solid CaCO_3 produced in the shells of marine organisms, estimated at just 0.7 Gt C/yr (IPCC TAR-3, 2001: 198). Coral reefs, thriving in warm seawater, contribute a tiny fraction at 0.084 Gt C/yr CaCO_3 production and, despite hype, globally store only <0.3 Gt of this inorganic C.

Compared to Figure 34, Murphy (2025: fig. 1) shows novel CCS achievement as a more modest 0.0004 Gt C/yr, or just <0.0013% of total. Comparatively, S/ECCS actuality is ~1 Gt C/yr and potentially 2 Gt C/yr, and reforestation ~+0.7 Gt C/yr, as both reported herein.

Multiple benefits of earthworms on plants, litter, soil and other soil biota are irreplaceable by mechanical or chemical means. A global fresh weight ‘vermi-mass’ of 4–8 Gt, doubled for terrain relief to a massive 8–16 Gt (with carbon content up to 4 Gt C) if earthworms process approximately their body weight per day, then these values per year are in the region of (10 x 365 =) 3,650 Gt of soil and perhaps almost all of the annual NPP.

The recent highly promoted and marketed “Biochar” or pyrolysis schemes are a very minor part of the broader CCS activities, themselves almost irrelevant. (Also, as an agricultural amendment these “chars” offer zero advantage over proven composts). At their most extravagant the best expectation for all unproven CCS is still only a miniscule 0.1 Gt C/yr sequestration at enormous and quite unjustifiable costs (Kazlou et al. 2024). Murphy (2025) charts US\$114 squandered on “Biochar” research that delivers, at optimistic best, 0.00027 Gt C/yr storage (cf. S/ECCS ~1 Gt C/yr and reforestation 0.7 Gt C/yr). Organic farms and earthworms alone offer best proven results, practically for free.

4.6 Permaculture “Greening the Desert” Project

A practical demonstration site is found in Jordan where an essential, initial step was to fence the property to exclude goats as such livestock, despite contrary claims by global Savory Institute, denude remaining vegetation in marginal lands thereby expanding deserts. This link provides details - <https://www.greeningthedesertproject.org/>. The project celebrated the return of fungi and earthworms as key indicators of its success. Similar de-desertification is entirely possible in other regions, such as Australia or Africa.

5 Discussion

5.1 On Soil (and Worms), Climate, and Food

Despite their fundamental importance to all aspects of life on Earth, the scope, state and status of soils remain remarkably poorly resolved. Michaelangelo’s comment from 1500

still rings true that we know more about the celestial bodies (and the “boasted glories” of the oceans) than we do of the Soil directly beneath our feet. Case in point, and reflecting the remark about increasing desertification, is that Gibbs & Salmon (2015: tab.2) showed degraded land estimates may vary from less than 1 billion ha (1 Gha) to over 6 billion ha, a massive six-fold variation. But they considered higher figures having the most weight.

Our lack of basic information is exemplified by expert authorities claiming that Australian soil carbon totals 30 Gt SOC, whereas my data shows 900 Gt SOC, or thirty times more.

Hopefully such discrepancies will be corrected before IPCC's Seventh Assessment Report (AR7) that is expected to be completed by late 2029. Some of their data, as noted in the Introduction, is provided by the Global Carbon Budget (GCB 2024 - <https://globalcarbonbudget.org>) which, in the latest report, had emissions of 37.4 billion tonnes of CO₂ (10.1/yr Gt C) from Fossil Fuels (FF) and 4.2 billion tonnes of CO₂ (1.1 Gt C/yr) from Land-use change (LUC), a ratio of 90% to 10%. However, proper accounting, as herein, shows gross FF emissions are unchanged, but gross Land emissions are likely similar at around 440 Gt C/yr with real ratio then reversed as 2% to 98%. A recent review had a Land sink overestimated by 23% and the LUC emissions increased by 14% (Dorgeist *et al.* 2024), which gives support to the current thesis but these are themselves underestimations: Land is no longer a sink and LUC is much higher. A report by Hengl *et al.* (2026) adds further weight to this argument, it confirms soil is now a net carbon source.

GCB (2025) state: “Emissions from permanent deforestation, the main driver of global gross sources from land-use change, remain high at around 3.9 GtCO₂ per year [1.1 Gt C/yr] over the 2015-2024 period. Permanent removals through re/afforestation offset around half of the permanent deforestation emissions (2.2 GtCO₂ per year) [0.6 Gt C/yr].” Yet the inability of a massive Land sink to fully absorb the entire 450 Gt C/yr of CO₂ released is due to critical LUC from deforestation and soil erosion/toxicity causing its failure to compensate. The resulting net excess of 2.8 ppm atmospheric CO₂ is equal to 5.96 Gt C (gigatonnes of carbon, or less than 1.4% of Land's absorption rate also of 440 Gt C/yr). This excess is equal to half the net LUC shown in the revised global Carbon Cycle figure of ~12.4 Gt C/yr indicating a need to aim for a 50% reduction of LUC. The two main policies of 50% reduction in red meat over-consumption, and 100% Organic farming would increase land's capacity to absorb this excess by greater photosynthesis for SOC.

This is not at all an unrealistic objective and, rationally, there are no other practical options. According to Gibbs & Salmon (2015) the FAO TerraSTAT interpretation of GLASOD had determined that over 6 Gha, or 66 percent of the world's land, had been affected by degradation, leaving roughly only a third of Land's surface in good condition. The UN's Land Outlook Report (2021) concluded: “Land is the operative link between biodiversity loss and climate change, and therefore must be the primary focus of any meaningful intervention to tackle these intertwined crises. Restoring degraded land and soil provides the most fertile ground on which to take immediate and concerted action.”

Conversely, Anderson et al. (2019) reported that Natural climate solutions are not enough and decarbonization of industry and fossil fuels must be reinforced. This too seems the main theme of IPCC in all its manifestations, including the latest (IPCC 2021 and COP30). There are two major flaws in both latter arguments: Firstly, that all terrestrial calculations are based upon extrapolations that simplistically report land as being planimetrically flat, whereas in reality land is hilly and soil is bumpy, to at least double the true surface area and hence many, if not all, of these soil losses and models for restoration. Secondly, reducing industrial and energy outputs by up to 26% was already tested on a global scale during the 2019-2022 COVID shutdowns that had no noticeable effect on NOAA's CO₂ charts. The COVID shutdown effects are summarized here as: *“Daily global CO₂ emissions decreased by –17% (–11 to –25% for ±1σ) by early April 2020 compared with the mean 2019 levels, just under half from changes in surface transport. At their peak, emissions in individual countries decreased by –26% on average”* (Le Quéré et al. 2020). This clearly indicates that resolution is to be found mainly in Soil, not just in Fossil Fuels.

A theory proposed in 2019, based upon NASA/IPCC data, that shutdown of non-essential business for just six days would enable land plants to entirely fix annual CO₂ excess of 4 Gt C/yr was soon tested by these 2020-2021 COVID lockdowns which made no difference to the atmospheric carbon accumulation (Blakemore 2019 - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/veop-vol-3-2019-updated-july-2019.pdf>). Falsification of the theory was rather that IPCC massively underestimated and failed to report Soil erosion as the main source of CO₂, not FF alone. This further supports this current counter-theory that Soil loss is the main carbon issue.

While not arguing against reducing fossil fuels emissions, this report shows it should be a much lower priority than restoring soils. Energy resource conservation is essential for agricultural and industrial equipment, but there are other options for energy supply and efficiency provided for by Permaculture. Examples are solar-passive building designs, terrestrial heat-pumps, and Geothermal energy, or compressed-air Trompe systems. Geothermal energy is readily available and obvious in Japan, but is possible in any region.

As the current report shows, soil metrics are very poorly known, being both understudied and underreported. Nevertheless, the context of global issues has been condensed to nine or ten boundaries of concern – a type of ecological triage – by Rockstrom et al. (2009). These are shown below, updated and revised with spurious Ocean Acidification replaced by critical Soil Acidification. Contributions of poor agricultural practices are represented (in light green) as being major contributors to most transgressions. Of note is Climate Change not a top priority; most pressing are Soils and extinctions (Figure 35).

Figure 35. Planetary Boundaries as revised with Agriculture influences added (light green). Source - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2021/03/11/transgression/>.

Authors of the initial review (Rockström et al. 2009) identified both “rate of biodiversity loss” and synthetic N-P fertilizer overuse as most severe and pressing of global problems, more so than climate change, solutions for which they suggest as an immediate 25% reduction in N fertilizers and: “Agricultural systems that better mimic natural processes (e.g., complex agro-ecosystems)”, in other words: A call for 100% Organic agriculture. Shortcomings in a subsequent Rockstrom et al. (2023) update are commented upon here - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2023/11/08/comment-on-new-planetary-boundaries/>.

In response to these environmental crises, consequential social and economic issues are claimed to be addressed in the UN’s SDGs of their Agenda 2030. However, because Soil – which is fundamental to issues of species extinction, climate and food security – are almost completely ignored (SDG’s mention “soil” only twice in passing!) all other derived issues and solutions will inevitably fail. Thus, a complete overhaul and revision of SDGs is needed to properly appreciate the soil foundation upon which all other issues rest. The graphic below revises SDGs for more ecologically realistic ambitions (Figure 36).

Global SDGs Need 0 SOIL as New “Ground Zero SDG”

Figure 36. SDGs in need of fundamental redrafting for a more solid Soil foundation that underlie and determine all other issues, or a call for a new “Ground Zero” redefining. Source - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2021/03/30/soil-nexus/> .

5.2 Practical Solutions in Context and Imperative to “De-cide” (i.e., to Reduce Toxins)

Considering the problems and solutions in relative proportions, Project Drawdown compiled a type of context and triage system (as advocated by this current report) with practical and prioritized suggestions as remedies to issues. Their conclusions support those advocated herein with recommendations weighted for effectiveness at international policy levels and also at a more personal or household levels (Figures 37).

Figure 37. Global policy options in perspective. Soil is optimal, CCS is minor, and Ocean miniscule. Ratios of maximal Gt CO₂eq sequestration in 2020-2050 are Soil: 392 (98.5%), CCS: 4.4 (1%), and Ocean: 1.5 (0.4%), respectively. Source – Drawdown Review 2020 - <https://drawdown.org/sites/default/files/pdfs/TheDrawdownReview%E2%80%93932020%E2%80%9393Download.pdf>.

Based upon GCB data, the “Blue Carbon” in seagrasses, tidal marshes, and mangroves total just 8–32 Gt organic carbon (Walden et al. 2024, Krause et al. 2025). This is <0.1% of the total terrestrial carbon, found mainly in Soil, at >33,000 Gt C. The relatively low importance of Ocean or CCS are clearly demonstrated in the Drawdown Review as in the current report. Appropriate policy would be to redirect all massive funds from irrelevant Marine projects or speculative CCS, to actually confront the triple issues of extinction, climate and food security, by reallocating all resources to researching Soil and Organics.

The seemingly low value of just 1.0 Gt for issue of “Address Wastes & Diets” (at household level) does not represent its disproportionate synergy because this would be the major driver for the other Land cures. Indeed, this is reflected in the relative merits for individual actions that are defined with primary emphasis precisely on Waste and Diet in Figure 38.

Figure 38. Relative effectiveness of individual actions; most beneficial are: 1/. Composting all food “wastes”, 2/. Reducing excessive red-meat. These are the exact same arguments presented in this report. Source –<https://drawdown.org/insights/the-powerful-role-of-household-actions-in-solving-climate-change> .

As well as promoting a plant-based diet (i.e., meat reduction), further conversion to Organic would restore soil carbon lost from chemical farms while providing food security in terms of escape from agrichemical and GMO dependencies thereby lessening need for irrigation or pollution control. Penalties for Organic production are higher labour requirements, but these are considered positives where they reduce rapid urbanization

and unemployment whilst providing healthy activities in Nature. Simultaneous with Organic husbandry, an enormous “unseen labour force” comes into play with enhancement of native soil fauna (worms) multi-tasking issues corrupted by chemicals.

The need for personal protective equipment to distribute, mix or spray toxic agrichemicals (assuming complex dilution, dates, rates and handling advice are followed) indicate the inherent dangers of these synthetics. Regarding pollution, although proper Organic farming now disavows human sewage often contaminated with pharmaceuticals, heavy metals and other long-term pollutants, this had traditional use. Rice traditionally used humanure and canal sediment dredgings to maintain paddy fertility. Rice husk residues are still burned today adding some extra charcoal. None of these practices are considered sensible with current burden of toxins and pollutants. Yet the importance of temporary anaerobic conditions for Soil Organic Matter (SOM) accumulation from wet rice-cropping in paddy soils, is in enrichment of SOM/SOC as shown over 2,000 years (Kalbitz et al., 2013). Organic paddy in Thailand had significantly higher SOC stock compared to conventional rice paddy (1,108 vs. 625 kg SOC/ha/year).

Organic rice in Philippines, and other crops like sugarcane, were described by Blakemore (2016) that provides a model for reducing pollution in Australia’s Great Barrier Reef (GBR) receiving multi-billion dollars in funds for conservation, but little or none of this goes towards the greatest issue, that of the source soil pollution (see Appendix). In this regard, of note is that whilst hundreds of soil organisms are recorded extinct, not a single coral species nor wholly marine fish is yet reported (and just one marine mammal in 250 yrs).

Issues of Ocean overemphasis and relative importance are discussed in the Appendix. Comparatively, soils are Australia’s most valuable and irreplaceable natural asset valued at about \$16 trillion of the world’s \$325 trillion total soil capital (Khuraijam et al. 2025), this despite soil being under-reported and underestimated. Support for raising Australian soil carbon is in Blakemore (2024) noting for Oceania (i.e., mainly Australia), mean soil depth is 33 m, as was indeed found by Harper & Tibbett (2013) sampling to 38 m in WA, Australia who also found five times greater soil carbon at depth (as Rolando et al. 2021 – a reference mistaken in section “3.4. Case Study of Soils Downunder in Australia”). Rolando et al. (2021: tab. 1) show 0–500 cm soil having x10 SOC compared to the top 0–30 cm. Thus, Australia’s ~30 Gt SOC in just the top 0–30 cm soils may total at least 300 Gt SOC to greater depth, × 2 for terrain and +50% for glomalin + saprock is ~900 Gt SOC. This is approximately the same as the current total atmospheric CO₂ of about 890 Gt C.

Returning to open and honest context and triage on ongoing destruction of soils and food; complete environmental collapse may be avoided if Scientific information and government policies report on and rectify the enormous costs of indulgent meat eating. At a personal level to avoid hypocrisy, anyone sincerely advocating for environmental (or ethical) issues must reduce or eschew their own meat consumption. As well as reducing deforestation, this also allows resource redirection of crop production for direct human

consumption, rather than inefficient nutrition via animals. Egg production or dairy are not as destructive, both can operate on pasture or fallow synergistically as part of regular, Organic, crop-rotation. Grazing and foraging can be readily intermeshed with silviculture or orchards with some livestock. Just one small example is an organic farm in Canberra with cattle and a flock of 4,000 a free-range chickens protected from predation by a small number of Maremma Italian-sheepdogs, the farm selling some of its produce at the gate.

Perversely, rather than meat moderation, some people advocate for greater meat consumption. Allied to this issue is the work of Allan Savory and his anecdotal “Holistic” pasture management alleged to combat desertification by moving more stock into marginal lands. This idea of taking cattle or other stock into deserts to restore them has immediate flaws as, by definition, arid lands lack sufficient food, or water; and a cow or bullock may drink up to 100 litres per head per day. Having goats in arid or Mediterranean climates are often, literally, the final straw*. The broader argument also implies need for more meat rather than viewing the amount of global deforestation required being wholly unjustifiable just to satiate this extravagant demand. Furthermore, most if not all of supposed Holistic management is already a part of Agroecology, although neither are currently considered wholly Organic management. Most of the recently promoted practices such as strip-grazing and fallow rotations as modified for cell grazing were already in common use in classical Organic husbandry, e.g. by Dr André Voisin. A critical review is by Hawkins et al. (2022). In contrast to Alan Savory’s meat promoting esoterism is an holistic rationale of a Scientific approach towards agroecology by Widdowson (1987).

Summary of very many reports, such as Rothamsted’s, show that long-term addition of organic matter improves crop yield, water holding capacity, porosity, and water stable aggregation while decreasing bulk density and surface crusting, and the incorporation into the soil matrix of surface litter. All of these effects may be attributed to the natural activities and synergistic stimulation of earthworms which by themselves increase, or at the very least, maintain SOC. No chemical nor physical interventions can mimic this.

Corollary of Regen is Rothamsted that may claim FYM is Organic and soil restorative but, as noted already, the issue of healthy and uncontaminated food is unresolved. Certainly, their organic FYM fertilizer has benefits, but the need is to properly compare to 100% Organic. To remain relevant, Rothamsted may embrace their successes but must admit failure of chemical farming, then start to demonstrate restoration of Organic from chemical production. Rothamsted may be an exemplar for proper Organic conversions.

As Blakemore (2018a) commented: *“On a positive note, an incontrovertible loss of regional plant biodiversity due to atmospheric and soil nitrogen pollution reversed in just 20 years after synthetic fertilizer application ceased on some Rothamsted plots. Although as yet unobserved in a wider landscape, such restoration, if pertaining to animals too, indicates a viable solution to earthworm depletions and, from this, a possible reversal in the insect and other species declines too.”* This is clear indication of the direction to head.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, it is fair and reasonable to state that just as the Rothamsted experiment has run its course and rather than proving the benefits and needs of a wholly chemical approach it has demonstrated the opposite: that Organic management, albeit improperly applied there, have been clearly proven as superior by all metrics. Similarly, there remains little justification for continuing to destroy fundamental life support systems – such as healthy food, soils, air, water and a vibrant biodiversity – with destructive chemical farming. Making no ecological sense, should the hidden costs (to health and the environment as well as to climate) be realized and were reparation applied and subsidies removed, then it makes no economic sense either. The restoration of proven but improvable Organic husbandry does make comply in all its aspects. There are few penalties or disbenefits. Yields are as high or higher, food quality is better, soils are healthier, and carbon sequestration is an integral part. Concepts are simple and scalable: To simply recycle organic “wastes” as composts, and to avoid toxic synthetics. This is Permaculture’s premise too, to move as little as possible from Natural processes.

Being more actively involved, in an introduction to the book *Harnessing the Earthworm*, Lady Eve Balfour, the founder and pioneer of organic Haughley, wrote: “*When the question is asked, ‘Can I build top-soil?’ the answer is ‘Yes’, and when the first question is followed by a second question, ‘How?’ the answer is ‘Feed earthworms’*”. This prescience insight is a path we should now follow to restore our soils and our health. Related to this, a recommendation is to read Sir Albert Howard’s excellent Introduction to the reprinting of Darwin’s book - https://journeytoforever.org/farm_library/oliver/howard_intro.html.

Finally, the paramount importance of preserving and restoring earthworms as key drivers of soil health in most situations is eloquently represented in the photo below (Figure 39).

Figure 39. Earthworm benefits no chemist, physicist nor microbiologist could possibly emulate. Unfortunately for commerce, earthworms work for free and are unpatentable for profit. Source - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2017/02/22/food-for-thought-ii/>

Restoring 100% Organic husbandry with earthworms validates Darwin (1881) who noted: “*I am led to conclude that all the vegetable mould [humus or SOC].. has passed many times through, and will again pass many times through, the intestinal canals of worms.*” Interestingly, one of Darwin’s descendants living in Sydney has come to similar conclusions to those presented in the current report – the need to reduce red-meat eating (see - <https://www.thedarwinchallenge.org/>).

That the present report is speculative in regard to some crucial areas of loss and restoration of topsoils, is due to lack of resources allocated to investigate these key issues, in particular want of a Soil Ecology Institute to research them. This is urgently required, and costs are deferred if resources currently misappropriated on less crucial Marine issues are redirected. Boasted claims justifying Ocean funds are often diminished and most of their issues solvable in Soil, so resource reallocation is entirely appropriate.

Some conclusions and recommendations are extended in more detail in an Appendix.

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REFERENCES [to be tediously and needlessly formatted in final redrafts]

Anderson, C. M., DeFries, R. S., Litterman, R., Matson, D. C., Nepstad, D. C., Pacala, S., Rastetter, E., Field, C.B. (2019). Natural climate solutions are not enough. *Science*, 363(6430), 933-934. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaw2741>.

Apostolakis, A., et al. (2025). Long-term reduced tillage does not enhance crop yield, soil organic carbon stocks or greenhouse gas mitigation under ambient rainfall and rainfall exclusion in a temperate Luvisol. *Soil and Tillage Research*. 257: 106985. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2025.106985>.

Asner, G. P., Scurlock, J. M. O., & Hicke, J. A. (2003). Global synthesis of leaf area index observations: implications for ecological and remote sensing studies. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 12(3), 191–205.

Badgley C., Moghtader J., Quintero E., et al. (2007). Organic agriculture and the global food supply. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*. 22(2):86-108. doi:10.1017/S1742170507001640.

Bai L., Duan J., Shi P., Xiao J., Li Z., Li P. (2025). Erosion-deposition processes drive soil organic carbon mineralization through aggregate breakdown and buildup. *CATENA*, 260. doi:10.1016/j.catena.2025.109432.

Bhardwaj R.L., Parashar A., Parewa H.P., Vyas L. (2024). An Alarming Decline in the Nutritional Quality of Foods: The Biggest Challenge for Future Generations' Health. *Foods*. 13(6):877. doi: 10.3390/foods13060877.

Bilir, T. E., Bloom, A. A., Konings, A. G., Liu, J., Parazoo, N. C., Quetin, G. R., et al. (2025). Satellite-constrained reanalysis reveals CO₂ versus climate process compensation across the global land carbon sink. *AGU Advances*. 6: e2025AV001689. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2025AV001689>.

Blake, L., Goulding, K. W. T., Mott, C. J. B., Johnston, A. E. (1999). Changes in soil chemistry accompanying acidification over more than 100 years under woodland and grass at Rothamsted Experimental Station, UK. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 50(3), 401–412. Portico. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2389.1999.00253.x>

Blakemore R.J. (1981). Ecology of earthworms under different fertilizer regimes in agriculture. Unpub. BSc. Hons. Thesis, Westminster Uni., Thesis number 801/1/22.

Blakemore, R.J. (2000). Ecology of earthworms under the “Haughley Experiment” of organic and conventional management regimes. *Biol. Agric. Hortic*. 18, 141–159. Available online: <http://orgprints.org/30000/> .

Blakemore, R.J. (2016). *Veni, Vidi, Vermi...II*. Earthworms in Organic Fields Restore SOM & H₂O and Fix CO₂. *Veop*: 2 (2): 1-26. [Online – <https://veop.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/09/vvv-ii.pdf>].

Blakemore, R. J. (2018a). Critical Decline of Earthworms from Organic Origins under Intensive, Humic SOM-Depleting Agriculture. *Soil Systems*, 2(2), 33. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soilsystems2020033>.

Blakemore, R. J. (2018b). Non-Flat Earth Recalibrated for Terrain and Topsoil. *Soil Systems*, 2(4), 64. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soilsystems2040064>.

Blakemore R.J. (2019). <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.aav0550>.

Blakemore, R.J. (2023). Biotic SOC Stock: What We Had & What We Lost. *Veop*. 6: 1-59. <https://veop.wordpress.com/new-publications/> . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7825446. <https://veop.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/veop-6.pdf>.

- Blakemore, R. J. (2024). Biomass Refined: 99% of Organic Carbon in Soils. *Biomass*, 4(4), 1257-1300. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomass4040070>.
- Blakemore R.J. (2025). Biodiversity restated: > 99.9% of global species in Soil Biota. *ZooKeys* 1224: 283-316. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1224.131153>.
- Borrelli, P., Robinson, D.A., Fleischer, L.R. *et al.* (2017). An assessment of the global impact of 21st century land use change on soil erosion. *Nat Commun* **8**: 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02142-7>.
- Brunner, I. *et al.* (2013). Belowground C turnover of European forests: Fine roots, mycorrhizal mycelia, soil organic matter and soil models. A Technical Report. https://pure.uva.nl/ws/files/2034462/147190_belowground.pdf.
- Buringh, P. (1984). The Role of Terrestrial Vegetation in the Global Carbon Cycle. In: Remote Sensing. Ed. G. M. Woodwell. 1984 SCOPE (No. 232). Wiley & Sons. Pp. 91 – 109. https://scope.dge.carnegiescience.edu/SCOPE_23/SCOPE_23_3.1_chapter3_91-109.pdf.
- Ciais, P., Ke, P., Sitch, S., Chevallier, F., Liu, Z. (2025). Low latency carbon budget analysis reveals a large decline of the land carbon sink in 2023 and 2024, EGU General Assembly 2025, Vienna, Austria, 27 Apr–2 May 2025, EGU25-51, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-51>.
- Clark I.M., Buchkina N., Jhurrea D., Goulding K.W., Hirsch P.R. (2012). Impacts of nitrogen application rates on the activity and diversity of denitrifying bacteria in the Broadbalk Wheat Experiment. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci.* 5;367(1593):1235-44. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2011.0314.
- Copard, Y., Hatté, C., Cécillon, L., Barré, P., Chenu, C., Cornu, S. (2025). Soil carbon dynamics reshaped by ancient carbon quantification. *Global Change Biology.* 31(e70482). <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70482>.
- Crézé, C., Saatchi, S., Kwon, N., Yang, Y., and Li, S. (2025). High-resolution global map (100 m) of soil organic carbon reveals critical ecosystems for carbon storage. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* [Preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-294>, in review, 2025. <https://essd.copernicus.org/preprints/essd-2025-294/essd-2025-294.pdf>.
- Crowther, E. M. (1925). Studies on soil reaction: IV. The soil reaction of continuously manured plots at Rothamsted and Woburn. *The Journal of Agricultural Science.* 15(2): 222–231. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0021859600005682>.
- Crowther, T.W., *et al.* (2019). The global soil community and its influence on biogeochemistry. *Science.* 365(6455): 772-773. DOI: 10.1126/science.aav0550. <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.aav0550>.

Darwin, C. (1881). The formation of vegetable mould, through the action of worms, with observations on their habits. London: John Murray.

Davis, D.R. (2009). Declining Fruit and Vegetable Nutrient Composition: What Is the Evidence? *HortScience*. 44(1): 15–19. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTSCI.44.1.15>.

Dinakaran, J., Hanief, M., Meena, A., Rao, K. S. (2014). The chronological advancement of soil organic carbon sequestration research: a review. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, India Section B: Biological Sciences*, 84(3), 487–504.

Dorgeist, L., et al. (2024). A consistent budgeting of terrestrial carbon fluxes. *Nat Commun*. 15, 7426. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-51126-x>.

Ebi, K. L., Loladze, I., Zhu, J., Zhu, C., Myers, S. S., Seneweera, S., et al. (2021). Nutritional quality of crops in a high CO₂ world: An agenda for research and technology development. *Environmental Research Letters*. 16(6):064045. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/abfcfa>.

Erb, KH., et al. (2018). Unexpectedly large impact of forest management and grazing on global vegetation biomass. *Nature* 553, 73–76. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature25138>.

Fan MS, Zhao FJ, Fairweather-Tait SJ, Poulton PR, Dunham SJ, McGrath SP. (2008). Evidence of decreasing mineral density in wheat grain over the last 160 years. *J Trace Elem Med Biol*. 22(4):315-24. doi: 10.1016/j.jtemb.2008.07.002.

FAO (2025) Global Forest Resources Assessment, Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cd6709en>.

Feber, G.J., et al. (2026). How deep is your soil? Quantifying and spatially analyzing understudied deep soil in the United States. *Geoderma*. 466: 117697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2026.117697>.

Fyfe, R. M., Coombe, R., Davies, H., Parry, L. (2014). The importance of sub-peat carbon storage as shown by data from Dartmoor, UK. *Soil Use & Management*, 30(1), 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.12091>.

Garvin, D.F., Welch, R.M., Finley, J.W. (2006). Historical shifts in the seed mineral micronutrient concentration of U.S. hard red winter wheat germplasm. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*. 86:2213-2220.

Ganzenmüller, R., Obermeier, W. A., Bultan, S., Spawn-Lee, S. A., Zabel, F., & Pongratz, J. (2025). Humans have depleted global terrestrial carbon stocks by a quarter. *One Earth*, 2(8), 811-822. DOI: 10.1016/j.oneear.2025.101392.

GCB (2025). Global Carbon Budget 2025, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-659>, in review, 2025. <https://essd.copernicus.org/preprints/essd-2025-659/essd-2025-659.pdf>.

- Gibbs, H.K., Salmon, J.M (2015). Mapping of the world's degraded lands. *Applied Geography*. 57: 12-21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2014.11.024>.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0143622814002793>.
- Gomiero, T., Pimentel, D., Paoletti, M.G. (2011). Environmental Impact of Different Agricultural Management Practices: Conventional vs. Organic Agriculture. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*. 30(1–2), 95–124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07352689.2011.554355>
- Goulding, K. W. T., Bailey, N. J., Hanley, B., Murphy, D. V., Poulton, P. R., & Webster, C. P. (1998). Microbial nitrification of redeposited NH₃ causes acidification of soil and water. *New Phytologist*, 140(1), 79-92. DOI 10.1046/j.1469-8137.1998.00182.x.
- Graven, H. D., et al. (2024). Bomb radiocarbon evidence for strong global carbon uptake and turnover in terrestrial vegetation. *Science*. 384(6702): 1335–1339. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adl4443>.
- Guo, Z.; Wang, Y.; Liu, J.; He, L.; Zhu, X.; Zuo, Y.; Wang, N.; Yuan, F.; Sun, Y.; Zhang, L.; et al. (2024). Mapping turnover of dissolved organic carbon in global topsoil. *Sci. Total Environ*. 906: 167621.
- Harper, R.J.; Tibbett, M. (2013). The hidden organic carbon in deep mineral soils. *Plant and Soil*. 368: 641–648. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-013-1600-9>.
- Hashimoto, S., Carvalhais, N., Ito, A., Migliavacca, M., Nishina, K., Reichstein, M. (2015). Global spatiotemporal distribution of soil respiration modeled using a global database. *Biogeosciences*. 12: 4121–4132. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-12-4121-2015>.
- Haverd, V., Smith, B., Canadell, J. G., Cuntz, M., Mikaloff-Fletcher, S., Farquhar, G., Woodgate, W., Briggs, P. R., and Trudinger, C. M. (2020). Higher than expected CO₂ fertilization inferred from leaf to global observations, *Glob. Chang. Biol*. 26: 2390–2402. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14950>.
- Hawkins, H-J., Venter, Z.S., Cramer, M.D. (2022). A holistic view of holistic management: What do farm-scale, carbon, and social studies tell us? *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 323: 107702. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107702> .
- He, J.-D.; Chi, G.-G.; Zou, Y.-N.; Shu, B.; Wu, Q.-S.; Srivastava, A.; Kuča, K. (2020). Contribution of glomalin-related soil proteins to soil organic carbon in trifoliolate orange. *Appl. Soil Ecol*. 154: 103592. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2020.103592>.
- Hengl, T., Consoli, D., Tian, X., Nauman, T. W., Nussbaum, M., Isik, M. S., Parente, L., Ho, Y.-F., Simoes, R., Gupta, S., Samuel-Rosa, A., Horst, T. Z., Safanelli, J. L., Harris, N. (2026). *OpenLandMap-soildb: global soil information at 30 m spatial resolution for 2000–2022+ based on spatiotemporal Machine Learning and harmonized legacy soil samples and observations*. ESSD Copernicus Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-336>.

Hirte, J., Walder, F., Hess, J., Büchi, L., Colombi, T., van der Heijden, M. G., Mayer, J. (2021). Enhanced root carbon allocation through organic farming is restricted to topsoils. *Science of The Total Environment*. 755: 143551. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.143551>.

Holden, P. (2001). Organic farming, food quality and human health: a review of the evidence. *Soil Association-Organic Standard*. 88p. https://www.soilassociation.org/media/4920/policy_report_2001_organic_farming_food_quality_human_health.pdf.

Houghton, R.A. (2007). Balancing the Global Carbon Budget. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 35, 313-347. doi:10.1146/annurev.earth.35.031306.140057.

Houghton, R.A. (2010). How well do we know the flux of CO₂ from land-use change? *Tellus B: Chemical and Physical Meteorology*. 62(5): 337–351. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0889.2010.00473.x>. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/j.1600-0889.2010.00473.x>

Houghton, R.A., Castanho, A. (2023). Annual emissions of carbon from land use, land-use change, and forestry from 1850 to 2020, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 15, 2025–2054, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-2025-2023>.

Howard, A. (1940). *An agricultural testament*. Oxford University Press.

Huang, J., et al. (2018). The global oxygen budget and its future projection. *Science Bulletin*. 63(18). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2018.07.023>.

IPBES (2019): Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. E. S. Brondizio, J. Settele, S. Díaz, and H. T. Ngo (editors). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. 1148 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831673>.

IPCC TAR-3 (2001) - <https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/02/TAR-03.pdf>.

IPCC (2021). *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis*. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Masson-Delmotte, V., et al. (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 2391 pp. doi:10.1017/9781009157896.

Iwahashi, J. (2025). Depth to bedrock in Japan: insights from borehole data and terrain analysis using digital elevation models. *Prog Earth Planet Sci*. 12: 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40645-025-00698-3>.

Jackson, R. B., Lajtha, K., Crow, S. E., Cotrufo, M. F., Kramer, M. G., Piñeiro, G. (2017). The ecology of soil carbon: Pools, vulnerabilities, and biotic and abiotic controls. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 48, 419-446.

Jenkinson, D. S. & Powlson, D. S. (1976). The effects of biocidal treatments on metabolism in soil – V. A method for measuring soil biomass. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 8, 209-213.

Jin, C., Jian, J., Bourque, C.P.-A., Zha, T., Dai, L., Yang, Y., et al. (2024). Soil autotrophic-to-heterotrophic-respiration ratio and its controlling factors across several terrestrial biomes: A global synthesis. *Catena*. 242: 108118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2024.108118>.

Johnston, A. E., Goulding, K. W. T., & Poulton, P. R. (1986). Soil acidification during more than 100 years under permanent grassland and woodland at Rothamsted. *Soil Use and Management*, 2(1), 3–10. Portico. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-2743.1986.tb00669.x>

Kalbitz, K., et al. (2013). The carbon count of 2000 years of rice cultivation. *Global Change Biology*, 19(11), 3360-3373. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12080>.

Kaplan, J. O., Krumhardt, K. M., Ellis, E. C., Ruddiman, W. F., Lemmen, C., Klein Goldewijk, K. (2010). Holocene carbon emissions as a result of anthropogenic land cover change. *The Holocene*, 21(5), 775–791. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683610386983>.

Kavamura VN, Hayat R, Clark IM, Rossmann M, Mendes R, Hirsch PR and Mauchline TH (2018) Inorganic Nitrogen Application Affects Both Taxonomical and Predicted Functional Structure of Wheat Rhizosphere Bacterial Communities. *Front. Microbiol.* 9:1074. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.01074>.

Kazlou, T., Cherp, A., Jewell, J. (2024). Feasible deployment of carbon capture and storage and the requirements of climate targets. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 14: 1047–1055. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-024-02104-0>.

Khuraijam, S. et al. (2025). Understanding the impact of identity and socio-economic factors on the adoption of soil conservation practices: Empirical evidence from Australia. *Journal of Rural Studies*. 116:103636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2025.103636>.

Kopittke, P.M., Dalal, R., McKenna, B.A., Smith, P., Wang, P., Weng, Z., van der Bom, F. J. T., Menzies, N.W. (2024). Soil is a major contributor to global greenhouse gas emissions and climate change. *SOIL*, 10, 873–885, <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-10-873-2024>. <https://soil.copernicus.org/articles/10/873/2024/>.

Koren, G., et al. (2019). Global 3-D Simulations of the Triple Oxygen Isotope Signature $\Delta^{17}\text{O}$ in CO_2 : Spatiotemporal Gradients and Sensitivities to the Terrestrial Carbon Cycle, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 124, 6087–6106. DOI: 10.1029/2019JD030387.

Krause, J.R., Cameron, C., Arias-Ortiz, A. et al. Global seagrass carbon stock variability and emissions from seagrass loss. *Nat Commun* 16, 3798 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-59204-4>.

- Lal, R. 2006. Influence of Soil Erosion on Carbon Dynamics in the World. Chapter 3. In: Science in Soil Science SOIL EROSION AND CARBON DYNAMICS Edited by Eric J. Roose et al. Pp 23-35. Online: <https://library.oapen.org/bitstream/20.500.12657/41645/1/9781135460556.pdf>.
- Lambkin, D. C., Gwilliam, K. H., Layton, C., Canti, M. G., Pearce, T. G., Hodson, M. E. (2011). Production and dissolution rates of earthworm-secreted calcium carbonate. *Pedobiologia*. 54(SUPPL.), S119-S129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedobi.2011.09.003>.
- Lawes JB, Gilbert JH (1851). On agricultural chemistry, especially in relation to the mineral theory of Baron Liebig. *J R Agric Soc.* 12:1–40. <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=osu.32435015987035&seq=3>.
- Lawes, J.B., Gilbert, J.H. (1885). XLIV: On some points in the composition of soils; with results illustrating the sources of the fertility of Manitoba prairie soils. *J. Chem. Soc. Trans.* 47: 380–422. <https://doi.org/10.1039/CT8854700380>. <https://pubs.rsc.org/is/content/articlelanding/1885/ct/ct8854700380#!divAbstract>.
- Le Quéré, C., Jackson, R.B., Jones, M.W. et al. (2020). Temporary reduction in daily global CO₂ emissions during the COVID-19 forced confinement. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* **10**, 647–653. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-0797-x>.
- Liang, MC, Laskar AH, Barkan E, Newman S, Thiemens MH, Rangarajan R. (2023). New constraints of terrestrial and oceanic global gross primary productions from the triple oxygen isotopic composition of atmospheric CO₂ and O₂. *Sci Rep.* 13(1):2162. doi: 10.1038/s41598-023-29389-z. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9905602/>.
- Lin, Z., Dai, Y., Mishra, U., Wang, G., Shangguan, W., Zhang, W., and Qin, Z. (2024). Global and regional soil organic carbon estimates: Magnitude and uncertainties. *Pedosphere*, 34(4), 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedsph.2023.06.005>.
- Liu, C., Jiang, H., Guo, X. (2025). Converging Patterns of Heterotrophic Respiration Between Growing and Non-Growing Seasons in Northern Temperate Grasslands. *Plants*. 14(16):2590. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants14162590>.
- Loladze I. (2002). Rising atmospheric CO₂ and human nutrition: toward globally imbalanced plant stoichiometry? *Trends Ecol. Evol* 17, 457–461. (10.1016/S0169-5347(02)02587-9). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(02\)02587-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(02)02587-9).
- Loladze I. (2014). Hidden shift of the ionome of plants exposed to elevated CO₂ depletes minerals at the base of human nutrition. *eLife* 3:e02245. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.02245.
- Lori M, Symnaczyk S, Mäder P, De Deyn G, Gattinger A (2017) Organic farming enhances soil microbial abundance and activity—A meta-analysis and meta-regression. *PLoS ONE* 12(7): e0180442. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0180442> .

Mariem, S.B., Gámez, A.L., Larraya, L. et al. (2020). Assessing the evolution of wheat grain traits during the last 166 years using archived samples. *Sci Rep* 10, 21828. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78504-x>.

Mayer, A.B., Trenchard, L., Rayns, F. (2022). Historical changes in the mineral content of fruit and vegetables in the UK from 1940 to 2019: a concern for human nutrition and agriculture. *Int J Food Sci Nutr.*;73(3): 315-326.

Meng, C., et al. (2019). Global soil acidification impacts on belowground processes. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 14:074003. DOI 10.1088/1748-9326/ab239c.

Ming, G., Zhang, Q., Gong, W., Li, Y., Shi, Y., Wang, Y. (2023). The characteristics of ecosystem respiration and its components of a representative film-mulched and drip-irrigated cotton field in Northwest China. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment.* 352:108506. ScienceDirect. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108506>.

Mo, L., Zohner, C. M., Reich, P. B., et al. (2023). Integrated global assessment of the natural forest carbon potential. *Nature*, 624(7990), 92–101. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06723-z>.

Moinet, G.Y.K., Hijbeek, R., van Vuuren, D. P., Giller, K.E. (2023). Carbon for soils, not soils for carbon. *Global Change Biology.* 29(9): 2384-2398. doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16570.

Mollison, B. (1988). *Permaculture: A Designers' Manual*; Tagari Publications: Sisters Creek, Tasmania, Australia.

Moreland, K., Tian, Z., Berhe, A. A., McFarlane, K. J., Hartsough, P., Hart, S. C., Bales, R., O'Geen, A. T. (2021). Deep in the Sierra Nevada critical zone: Saprock represents a large terrestrial organic carbon stock. *Environmental Research Letters.* 16(12): 124059. DOI 10.1088/1748-9326/ac3bfe.

Morris, H.M. The insect and other invertebrate fauna of arable land at Rothamsted. *Ann. Appl. Biol.* 1922, 9, 282–305. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]

Morris, H.M. The insect and other invertebrate fauna of arable land at Rothamsted. Part II. *Ann. Appl. Biol.* 1927, 14, 442–464. [Google Scholar].

Muller, A., Schader, C., El-Hage Scialabba, N. et al. (2017). Strategies for feeding the world more sustainably with organic agriculture. *Nat Commun* 8, 1290. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-01410-w>.

Murphy, D.J. (2025). Carbon Sequestration for Global-Scale Climate Change Mitigation: Overview of Strategies Plus Enhanced Roles for Perennial Crops. *Crops*, 5(3), 39. <https://doi.org/10.3390/crops5030039>.

Myers S.S., Smith M.R., Guth S., Golden C.D., Vaitla B., Mueller N.D., Dangour A.D., Huybers P. (2017). Climate change and global food systems: Potential impacts on food

security and undernutrition. *Annu. Rev. Public Health.* 38:259–277. doi: 10.1146/annurev-publhealth-031816-044356.

Nyffeler, M., Bonte, D. (2020). Where Have All the Spiders Gone? *Insects*, 11(4), 248. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects11040248>.

O’Kelly B.C. (2008). On the geotechnical design and use of peat bunds in the conservation of bogs, Proceedings of the International Conference on Geotechnical Engineering (ICGE’08), 24th–26th March, Hammamet, Tunisia. Vol. 1, pp. 259 – 267.

Owens, P.N. (2020). Soil erosion and sediment dynamics in the Anthropocene: a review of human impacts during a period of rapid global environmental change. *J Soils Sediments* 20, 4115–4143. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-020-02815-9>.

Pendleton, L., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., Albright, R., Kaup, A., Marshall, P., Marshall, N., Fletcher, S., Haraldsson, G., & Hansson, L. (2019). The Great Barrier Reef: Vulnerabilities and solutions in the face of ocean acidification. *Regional Studies in Marine Science*, 31, 100729. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsma.2019.100729>.

Pimentel, D. (2006). Soil Erosion: A Food and Environmental Threat. *Environ Dev Sustain.* 8: 119–137 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-005-1262-8>.

Pimentel, D., Burgess, M. (2013). Soil Erosion Threatens Food Production. *Agriculture.* 3(3), 443-463. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture3030443>.

Powlson, D. S., Poulton, P. R. (1998). Using the long-term experiments at rothamsted to address current agricultural and environmental issues. *Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science.* 42(6), 455–478. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03650349809385747>.

Poulton P, Johnston J, Macdonald A, White R, Powlson D. (2018). Major limitations to achieving "4 per 1000" increases in soil organic carbon stock in temperate regions: Evidence from long-term experiments at Rothamsted Research, United Kingdom. *Glob Chang Biol.* 24(6):2563-2584. doi: 10.1111/gcb.14066.

Pross, J., Tzedakis, P., Schmiedl, G., Christanis, K., Hooghiemstra, H., Müller, U. C., Kotthoff, U., Kalaitzidis, S., & Milner, A. (2007). Tenaghi Philippon (Greece) Revisited: Drilling a Continuous Lower-Latitude Terrestrial Climate Archive of the Last 250,000 Years. *Scientific Drilling.* 5: 44–46. <https://doi.org/10.2204/iodp.sd.5.06.2007>.

Qi, Y., Liu, C., Sun, S., Wang, S., Li, Y., Zhang, W. (2019). Plant root-shoot biomass allocation over diverse biomes: A global synthesis. *Global Ecology and Conservation.* 18: e00606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2019.e00606>.

Quartucci, F., et al. (2025). Depth-dependent temperature sensitivity of soil heterotrophic respiration in restored lands of the Atlantic Forest, Brazil. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment.* 378: 110132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2025.110132>.

Rahman A, Baharlouei P, Koh EHY, Pirvu DG, Rehmani R, Arcos M, Puri S. (2024). A Comprehensive Analysis of Organic Food: Evaluating Nutritional Value and Impact on Human Health. *Foods*. 13(2):208. doi: 10.3390/foods13020208.

Ren, T. and Cai, A. (2025). Global patterns and drivers of soil dissolved organic carbon concentrations, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*. 17, 2873–2885, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-2873-2025>.

Rockström, J.; Steffen, W.; Noone, K.; Persson, Å.; Chapin, F.S., III; Lambin, E.F. (2009). A safe operating space for humanity. *Nature*. 461, 472–475. <https://doi.org/10.1038/461472a>.

Rockström, J., et al. (2023). Safe and just Earth system boundaries. *Nature*, 619(7968), 102-111. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06083-8>.

Rodin, L.E.; Bazilevich, N.I.; Rozov, N.N. (1975). Productivity of the world's main ecosystems. In *Productivity of World Ecosystems*; Reichle, D.E., Franklin, J.F., Goodall, D.W., Eds.; National Academy of Sciences: Washington, DC, USA. Pp. 13–26. Available online: <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/read/20114/chapter/3>

Rolando, J.L.; Dubeux, J.C.B.; de Souza, T.C.; Mackowiak, C.; Wright, D.; George, S.; Pires, T.; Santos, E. (2021). Organic carbon is mostly stored in deep soil and only affected by land use in its superficial layers: A case study. *Agrosyst. Geosci. Environ.* 4, e20135. <https://access.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/agg2.20135>.

Rolfe J., Valck J. D. (2021). Values for protecting the Great Barrier Reef: A review and synthesis of studies over the past 35 years. *Mar. pollut. Bull.* 169, 112531. doi: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.112531.

Sanderman J., Hengl T., Fiske G.J. (2017). Soil carbon debt of 12,000 years of human land use. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 114(36):9575-9580. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1706103114.

Sanders, J., Brinkmann, J., Chmelikova, L. et al. Benefits of organic agriculture for environment and animal welfare in temperate climates. *Org. Agr.* 15, 213–231 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-025-00493-w>.

Santoro, M., et al. (2022). Global estimation of above-ground biomass from spaceborne C-band scatterometer observations aided by LiDAR metrics of vegetation structure. *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 281: 113180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2022.113114>.

Ruwaimana, M., Anshari, G. Z., Silva, L. C. R., Gavin, D. G. (2020). The oldest extant tropical peatland in the world: a major carbon reservoir for at least 47 000 years. *Environmental Research Letters*. 15(10): 104027. doi:10.1088/1748-9326/abb853.

Scheffe CR, Barlow KM, Robinson NJ, Crawford DM, McLaren TI, Smernik RJ, Croatto G, Walsh RD, Kitching M. (2015). 100 Years of superphosphate addition to pasture in an acid

soil—current nutrient status and future management. *Soil Research* 53, 662–676. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR14241>.

Sha, Z., Bai, Y., Li, R. et al. (2022). The global carbon sink potential of terrestrial vegetation can be increased substantially by optimal land management. *Commun Earth Environ* 3, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-021-00333-1>.

Shelef, E.; Rowland, J.C.; Wilson, C.J.; Hilley, G.E.; Mishra, U.; Altmann, G.L.; Ping, C. (2017). Large uncertainty in permafrost carbon stocks due to hillslope soil deposits. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 44, 6134–6144. doi:10.1002/2017GL073823.

Sierra, C., Ahrens, B., Bolinder, M., Braakhekke, M., von Fromm, S., Kätterer, T., Luo, Z., Parvin, N., Wang, G. (2024). Carbon sequestration in the subsoil and the time required to stabilize carbon for climate change mitigation. *Global Change Biol.*, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17153>.

Sizmur, T.; Martin, E.; Wagner, K.; Parmentier, E.; Watts, C.; Whitmore, A.P. (2017). Milled cereal straw accelerates earthworm (*Lumbricus terrestris*) growth more than selected organic amendments. *Appl. Soil Ecol.* 113, 166–177.

Skye, J., Melton, J. R., Goldblatt, C., Saumier, L., Gallego-Sala, A., Garneau, M., ... & Wang, Y. (2025a). Peat-DBase v.1: A compiled database of global peat depth measurements. *Earth System Science Data*, 17(17), 7313–7330. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-7313-2025>.

Skye et al. (2025b) - <https://essd.copernicus.org/preprints/essd-2025-432/essd-2025-432.pdf>.

Skye, J., Melton, J. R., Goldblatt, C., Gallego-Sala, A., Garneau, M., Winton, S. (2025c). PeatDepth-ML: A Global Map of Peat Depth Predicted using Machine Learning, *EGUsphere* [Preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-5363>.

Smith, L. G., et al. (2018). Modelling the production impacts of a widespread conversion to organic agriculture in England and Wales. *Land Use Policy* 76, no. C: 391-404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2018.02.035>.

Soriano, S., Walker, N. (1973). The Nitrifying Bacteria in Soils from Rothamsted Classical Fields and Elsewhere, *Journal of Applied Bacteriology*. 36(3) 523–529. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2672.1973.tb04135.x>

Standen, V. (1984). Production and Diversity of Enchytraeids, Earthworms and Plants in Fertilized Hay Meadow Plots. *The Journal of Applied Ecology*, 21(1), 293. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2403055>.

Strauss, J. et al. (2024): Organic matter storage and vulnerability in the permafrost domain. Elsevier, ISBN: 9780443299971. doi: 10.1016/b978-0-323-99931-1.00164-1. https://epic.awi.de/id/eprint/60122/1/final_3-s2.0-B9780323999311001641-main.pdf.

Tang, S., Pan, W., Yang, Y. *et al.* (2025). Soil carbon sequestration enhanced by long-term nitrogen and phosphorus fertilization. *Nat. Geosci.* 18: 1005–1013. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-025-01789-y>.

Tang, X., Fan, S., Zhang, W., Gao, S., Chen, G., and Shi, L. (2019). Global variability in belowground autotrophic respiration in terrestrial ecosystems, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 11, 1839–1852. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-11-1839-2019>.

Thomas, D. 2007. The Mineral Depletion of Foods Available to US as A Nation (1940–2002) – A Review of the 6th Edition of McCance and Widdowson. *Nutrition and Health*. 19(1-2): 21-55. [[CrossRef](#)]

Tian, H., *et al.* (2024). Global nitrous oxide budget (1980–2020). *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 16, 2543–2604, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-16-2543-2024>.

UNEP Emissions Gap Report (2025) - <https://www.unep.org/resources/emissions-gap-report-2025>.

UN Land Outlook Report (2021) (GLO2) - <https://www.unccd.int/resources/global-land-outlook/glo2-summary-decision-makers>.

Versteegh, E. A.A., Black, S., Canti, M. G. and Hodson, M. E. (2013) Earthworm-produced calcite granules: a new terrestrial palaeothermometer? *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 123. pp. 351-357. ISSN 0016-7037 doi: 10.1016/j.gca.2013.06.020.

Versteegh E.A.A., Black S., Hodson M.E. (2014): Environmental controls on the production of calcium carbonate by earthworms. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 70: 159–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2013.12.013>.

Vigar V, Myers S, Oliver C, Arellano J, Robinson S, Leifert C. (2019). A Systematic Review of Organic Versus Conventional Food Consumption: Is There a Measurable Benefit on Human Health? *Nutrients*. 12(1):7. doi: 10.3390/nu12010007.

Voigtländer, A., Rheinwalt, A., & Tofelde, S. (2024). Quantifying Earth's Topography: Steeper and Larger Than Projected in Digital Terrain Models. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 51(14), e2024GL109517. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL109517>.

Von Liebig, J. (1861). *Es ist ja die Spitze meines Lebens, Naturgesetze im Landbau*. Hrsg. Wolfgang von Haller. 4e Aufl. Bad Dürkheim 1995. 54 S.

Walden, L. *et al.* (2023). Multi-scale mapping of Australia's terrestrial and blue carbon stocks and their continental and bioregional drivers. *Commun. Earth Environ.* 4:189.

Wedderburn-Bisshop (2023) <https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/202310.1863/v1>.

Wedderburn-Bisshop, G. (2024a). Deforestation—a call for consistent carbon accounting. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 19 111006. DOI 10.1088/1748-9326/ad7d21; <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/ad7d21/pdf>.

- Wedderburn-Bisshop (2024b) <https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/202310.1863/v2>.
- Wedderburn-Bisshop G. (2025). Increased transparency in accounting conventions could benefit climate policy. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 20 044008. DOI: 10.1088/1748-9326/adb7f2.
- Whitman WB, Coleman DC, Wiebe WJ. (1998). Prokaryotes: the unseen majority. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 95(12):6578-83. doi: 10.1073/pnas.95.12.6578.
- Widdowson, R.W. (1987). *Towards Holistic Agriculture: A Scientific Approach*. Pergamon: London. ISBN 9780080342115.
- Widyastuti, M. T., Minasny, B., Padarian, J., et al. (2025). Digital mapping of peat thickness and carbon stock of global peatlands. *CATENA*, 258: 109243. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2025.109243>.
- Winkler, K., Fuchs, R., Rounsevell, M. et al. (2021). Global land use changes are four times greater than previously estimated. *Nat Commun.* **12**, 2501. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-22702-2>.
- Wu, H. et al. (2024). The overlooked role of deep soil in dissolved organic carbon transformation and CO₂ emissions: Evidence from incubation experiments and FT-ICR MS characterization. *Resour. Env. Sustain.* 7:100161. [10.1016/J.RESENV.2024.100161](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESENV.2024.100161).
- Xu. Z. et al. (2025). Mitigation of soil acidification is critical for reducing GHG emission and improving soil quality, crop yield and farm economic benefits: Evidence from a global meta-analysis. *Field Crops Res.* 322:109757. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2025.109757>.
- Young, I. M., Feeney, D. S., O'Donnell, A. G., Goulding, K. W. (2012). Fungi in century old managed soils could hold key to the development of soil water repellency. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry.* 45: 125-127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2011.10.007>.
- Zeng, J., Zhou, T., Cao, L. et al. (2025). Various responses of global heterotrophic respiration to variations in soil moisture and temperature enhance the positive feedback on atmospheric warming. *Commun Earth Environ.* 6:475. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-025-02423-w>.
- Zhang, L., Huang, Y., Rong, L. et al. Effect of soil erosion depth on crop yield based on topsoil removal method: a meta-analysis. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 41, 63 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-021-00718-8>.
- Ziska LH, Pettis JS, Edwards J, Hancock JE, Tomecek MB, Clark A, Dukes JS, Loladze I, Polley HW. (2016). Rising atmospheric CO₂ is reducing the protein concentration of a floral pollen source essential for North American bees. *Proc Biol Sci.* 283(1828):20160414. doi: 10.1098/rspb.2016.0414.

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APPENDIX [as Supplementary supporting material, Review not a requirement]

By R.J. Blakemore PhD, VermEcology, Japan; IUCN; Email: rob.blakemore@gmail.com.

The report this Appendix is attached to documents that the surface area of Earth has been doubled for topography, terrain and soil rugosity – thus Life on Earth is also doubled. It also provides a solution to Climate Change, to Extinctions, and human Cancer causes. This is being modest... the actual surface area of Earth is likely tripled or quadrupled, and most of the other causes of species' extinction and human ill-health are also resolved through Soils and Worms. Here more insight is provided into institutional deficiencies and policy biases as main reason for our failure to fix many problems of human excesses.

Institutional Bias and Soil Oversight

The present report is rather long and detailed, however, the IPCC (2021) report is longer at 2,409-pages and is highly biased as “Ocean” is cited 7,337 times but “Soil” only gets 1,061 hits, or just one seventh - this despite soils being key to both climate and food. “Land” gets about half the number of hits as Ocean at 4,428, but Land is arguably a thousand times more relevant and important in terms of carbon cycle, biodiversity and food security. IPCC references “soil organic carbon” just five times, while there are whole chapters on spurious “Ocean Acidification”. Soil acidification is not mentioned at all...

The IPCC team had 198 Coordinating Lead Authors, 36 Review Editors (total 234) with an additional 615 Contributing Authors (total 850). Of these, several belong to major Marine, Meteorological or Atmospheric Institutes, but I cannot find anyone affiliated with a dedicated Soil Ecology Institute. This is hardly surprising as none exists anywhere.

An online search overview says: *“There is no single “soil ecology research institute” but many research groups and institutions worldwide that focus on the subject, such as the National Centre for Soil Ecology (NCSE) in the Netherlands, a **virtual platform** which connects Dutch soil ecologists, and the Institute of Soil Biology and Biogeochemistry in the Czech Republic. Other examples include the James Hutton Institute in the UK, the [ZHAW Institute of Natural Resource Sciences](#) in Switzerland, and the Soil Ecology and Ecotoxicology Lab at the [University of Coimbra \(CFE\)](#) in Portugal.”* None of these compete in the scale and staffing of the many Marine facilities. This deficiency, or rather disparity, needs to be urgently addressed with proper priority and resource reallocation.

Bias is not only with IPCC, it is much more pernicious. As another example, ESSD (2025 - <https://essd.copernicus.org/articles/17/965/2025/essd-17-965-2025.pdf>) cites Ocean 450 times but Soil only gets a dozen mentions while, of the 88 institutions the authors are affiliated with, not one has mention of Soil in their title. Surely time for a “Sea Change”.

There is no shame in making honest errors in Science, but there is in failing to correct them. Throughout this report there are blatant omissions in reporting the importance of soil. Also clearly shown is how relatively immaterial are the boasted glories of the Ocean.

Basic photosynthesis equation shows CO_2 is source of all organic carbon, not humus. Whereas terrestrial plants take in and recycle the entire atmospheric stock within two years, marine plants use $\sim 40 \text{ Gt C/yr}$ (from about 700 Gt C) of dissolved CO_2 thus are not directly involved in active uptake nor direct recycling of atmospheric carbon dioxide.

Balanced stoichiometry for respiration and combustion (decomposition/fire) is the reverse: $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6 + 6\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 6\text{CO}_2 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, using O_2 and recycling CO_2 and water/steam.

Ecology is defined as the interaction between living organisms and their environment, both vital and inert (i.e., biological, physical or chemical). Biology is thus part of Ecology. Biological symbioses and antagonisms are a fundamental part of Ecology, as are plant and animal behaviours, while chemistry is of lesser concern. Farming is ecological too.

Unfortunately, most academic agronomists and agrichemical representatives promote agriculture as a mere chemical enterprise, yet the growing of crops is entirely ecological, much more complex than a few simple elemental reactions. Agricultural colleges typically conduct chemical or GMO trials using single plants in a soil that is sterilized (usually with chemicals or heat) in order to avoid the inconvenience of natural biological variation, for example the presence in a pot or a plot of a worm. The results of the treatment effects are then reported compared to the controls as if this is the definitive outcome. In reality, the ecological complexities of Nature are often outside the remit or realization of such narrow confines of a mere chemist or biochemical “engineer”. Proper and practical ecological outcomes may be better sought on adjacent fields on operational farms under different regimes, such as full chemical versus 100% organic. A meta-analysis of such side-by-side farm situations is reported on by Blakemore (2018a).

Possibly a pivotal point in the divergence of ecological from chemical farming was around 1881-1885, when Darwin (1881) published the first Soil Ecological study, and Frank (1885) published work on mycorrhizae. In contrast, Lawes & Gilbert (1885) argument for artificial manures (viz. Superphosphate synthetic fertilizer) that were established at Rothamsted.

The importance of Frank's work was almost entirely forgotten and swamped by the simplistic N-P-K chemical solutions on offer, yet may ultimately prevail with the most recent biological understanding of plant-microbe symbioses e.g. studies by Dent & Cocking (2017) argue that enhanced N-fixation may reduce the need for N fertilizers. And the arguments go back even further to Darwin (1836) and von Liebig (1840) and the humus theory of Jethro Tull [which incidentally is proving to be closer to the true situation since, seemingly, "90 or so minerals in the soil are essential" (Thomas, 2007)]. These nutrients are naturally supplied to plants at correct rates, in correct locations, and in synchrony, i.e., via natural biological activities – as Howard (1940) and Balfour (1975, 1977) explain. The rhythms of nature are seen in fluxes of components such as simplistic N-P-K here:

Haughley farm analysis image from
<https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2017/05/27/slimeless-spring-ii/> ;
<https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2020/10/16/nitrogen-necrosis/> and
<https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2022/05/04/worms-in-the-palace/>. Note that
 seasonal fluctuations, especially of Phosphates, makes random spot samples pointless.
 Also, up to 80% of P and 20% of nitrogen transfer to plants via the mycorrhizal symbioses.
 Similar seasonal or climatic fluctuations (temperature, rain) apply to levels of carbon,
 moisture, microbial activity, bulk density and various other key soil metrics (e.g.,
<https://www.ars.usda.gov/ARUserFiles/6233/seasonalVariationInSoilOrganic.pdf>).

Interestingly, the establishment of Rothamsted in 1839 is contemporary with Darwin's early studies, later compiled into one of the first Soil Ecology texts (Darwin, 1836, 1881). Lawes & Gilbert (1851 - babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=osu.32435015987035&seq=3) make some interesting observations on the early decadal results of their trials at Rothamsted, including the Broadbalk continuous wheat experiment where the farm-yard manure (FYM) plots outyielded most other chemical plots. In their conclusion they note that: "*Baron Liebig, indeed, himself asserts that farm-yard manure is the universal food of plants... all our calculations, therefore, should ne made on a full consideration of what is involved in its use. This is, however, not generally sufficiently borne in mind by chemists unconnected with practical agriculture... In fact, chemistry alone will do nothing for practical agriculture.*" Von Liebig, often called the father of Agricultural Chemistry, later in life realized that soil biology was paramount (Von Liebig 1861). The many subsequent chemists should realize the basic truism: that farming is wholly ecological. This was proven by Woolny (1890) who, in an attempt to disprove Darwin's earthworm benefit thesis, actually confirmed this as true and substantive. Due mainly to military and commercial interventions, the succeeding Century saw chemical farming rise to ascendancy being applied universally. Only recently is its failure accepted and attempts made to reverse damage caused to soil, to food and to health; still time enough.

A pivotal meeting was the 1939 Medical Testament of 600 Cheshire Doctors with presentations by Sir Robert McCarrison and Sir Albert Howard, the argument being that Organic farming was needed for healthy food to support healthy populations. This was a review of the success of the UK's National Health Service (NHS); an online Report is here - journeytoforever.org/farm_library/medtest/medtest_speeches.html#mccarrison. Unfortunately, the recommendations were not taken up due to the intervention of WW2.

As concerning is that some Agricultural institutions conduct comparative trials, as with Rothamsted, on small plots that are unrepresentative of whole-farm organic practices. Such unrealistic treatments are likely the "tokenism" destined to fail, nevertheless the results are published as definitively demonstrating the 'inferiority' of Organic practices.

Most often such highly biased research is funded by the chemical companies, directly or indirectly, thus it is in their profit interest to denigrate composts that are freely available to anyone, and the earthworm that is highly beneficial but unpatentable. For real progress, scientific researchers need honesty, independent of any merely venal interests.

Response to Facile Comment on Terrain Doubling Land Area and Carbon Totals

An uninvited comment by some Francophiles on Blakemore (2018b) titled "*Current Estimates of Soil Organic Carbon Stocks Are Not Four to Six Times Underestimated*" (<https://www.mdpi.com/2571-8789/4/3/45>) is unintentionally correct: SOC stocks are actually ten to thirty times underestimated, as this current study has clearly shown. While accepting that Earth is not flat (but entirely failing to give their estimate for true

surface area!), their main argument falsely claims soil samples are taken vertical to the soil surface whereas, as was clearly stated, soil samples are “perpendicular to the centre of the Earth”. The following figures show their facile argument (top left image) and their obvious shortcomings as a dump-truck has the same soil content but a smaller footprint.

Fig. 1 from www.mdpi.com/2571-8789/4/3/45

Compare to a soil tipper-truck (Wiki), is there same soil or not?

Images are from a response that the journal editors requested, which was withdrawn when they demanded an extra \$1,000 APC! Source: <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2019/09/20/soc-upped-after-uninvited-comment-on-soil-syst-2018-2-64/>.

These images elaborate the defence and, related to this, Shelef et al. (2017) already had similar conclusions of Permafrost carbon being x3 greater than estimates suggested and a need for sigmoid curves rather than linear for any slope calculations for a +40% extra C.

Government Policy and Public Funding

Policy needs are primarily for open and honest Scientific reporting and critical analysis of factual soil and biotic baseline data and any changes in these along with practical and beneficial remedies. This implies a need for independent researchers without commercial or other vested interests. A model for this is in the many Marine research facilities mostly having government support. With proper context and urgency of triage, as in the current report, there is an imperative to redirect funding more appropriately.

In this way the establishment of essential Soil Ecology Institutes would be cost free and, moreover, would be of benefit to taxpaying funders in terms of natural health outcomes.

There is concomitant need to demand 100% Organic food as it is now well established that the continued poisoning of the environment with artificial and toxic chemicals is immoral and illogical. The trope that more food is needed and this is only achievable with yet more synthetic input is false when the true yields, nutrient content and environmental benefits of natural food are properly studied and reported independently, as in this report.

Government subsidies removed from agrichemical and meat producers can similarly be re-directed to organic producers. This may involve encouraging of domestic and municipal composting. Trucks delivering food to cities should return to the farms with the market left-overs and other food or garden wastes for recycling via composts. Commercial entities and the companies responsible for deforestation, poisoning of the environment and food should recompense. At present the polluters often do not pay.

The argument that because Organic farmers' fields already have increased soil carbon and higher biodiversity they should not be entitled to carbon credits or other beneficial incentives as paid to Regen farmers need to be reevaluated. More properly, Organic farmers or Permaculture practitioners may be held as deserving models for emulation and instruction to those in transition or to rehabilitate chemical farmers from addictions.

Over-expenditure on Ocean (and Australia's GBR Rorts)

It is undeniable that coral reefs are cute and interesting with some diversity, for an Ocean habitat, but they cannot be argued to have much value to fisheries (that provide less than 1% of human food!), nor threat of extinction since no coral is yet reported extinct. Moreover, the justification for massive government subsidies for their research seem misplaced. For example, the Great Barrier Reef (GBR) in NE Australia has received \$billions in funding starting from 1960s. How much of this has gone towards supporting sugarcane farmers to convert to organic to help fix the reefs' pollution problems? The State of Queensland has around 350,000 ha of land used to provide 95% of Australia's sugarcane, and just a tiny fraction of 55 ha operated by Bundaberg Sugar is certified organic or in conversion as of early 2024, on currently available information. Yet a preliminary study in 2013 found that organic sugar cane in Philippines had higher yields,

more carbon and much greater soil biodiversity that conventional, chemical neighbours (Blakemore 2016, 2018a). Rational argument is that supporting Organic growers, rather than yet more marine misinformation, resolves soil issues whence the problems of the Sea mainly originate. Each year since 1960s GBR has “cried wolf” on corals, often falsely.

Some examples are falsely claims on economic value of the GBR. Overall, Australian GDP is AU\$2 trillion with Agriculture/food (<https://www.agriculture.gov.au/>) contributing AU\$100 billion (5%), while GBR’s mainly tourist value is claimed as AU\$9 billion (<0.5%) (<https://web.archive.org/web/20251218075342/https://www.barrierreef.org/uploads/GBRValue-FullReport-Oct25.pdf>). This value is not supported by data as their table 2.2. shows a total of 41.8 million visitor days, or (41.8/365 days) to give 114,520 visitors per day, whereas GBR truly had only 6,410 visitors per day, or part thereof, in 2024 (<https://www2.gbrmpa.gov.au/help/tourism-visitation-data>). Thus, this value seems conflated about 18 times suggesting actual, direct value of the reef is only AU\$0.5 billion (0.025% of GDP). Similarly, their claim of \$95 billion GBR evaluation is highly contrived speculation as it is only a cumulative hypothetical evaluation through to 2050, although this is rarely admitted. In other words, their table 1.1 is deliberately exaggerated about 25 times, reducing this hypothetical to just (95/25 yrs =) AU\$3.8 billion per year, although, as just shown, practically this is just AU\$0.5 billion per year, at most. They also give a total of \$124 billion economic opportunity over the next 50 years. As for elsewhere, most of Australia’s wealth truly depends entirely upon Nature and the health of its rapidly declining soils (www.acf.org.au/news/how-australias-prosperity-depends-on-nature).

This chronic GBR issue goes deeper as the AU\$95 value extends a 2017 report with an arbitrarily contrived AU\$56 billion having scant tangible evidence (Pendleton et al. 2019). Quoting their scholarly and scientific rigour, or lack thereof: “*This is Australia’s Reef. This is our natural asset. If we split the \$56 billion asset value down into its parts: • Australians who have visited the Reef as tourists – on their honeymoon, on a family holiday, on a bucket-list trip – derive \$29 billion in value • Australians that have not yet visited the Reef – but value knowing that it exists – derive \$24 billion in value • And the lucky Australians that are recreational users of the Reef – going to the beach, taking the boat out, diving on the weekends – derive \$3 billion in value.*” Such false facts and bad logic invite retraction and was indeed already criticized as being grossly overestimated by Rolf & Valk (2021).

From 2000 to 2010 a \$1 billion Census of Marine Life project determined that there are only 230,000 organisms in all Oceans, including microbial life, and speculated a total of 2 million spp. Thus, a similar diversity to all the World’s Oceans may be found in a handful of healthy soil. Yet there is very little support for soil biodiversity such are earthworm research compared, for example, to fully supported Polychaeta marine worm research that is of zero benefit thus must be exceedingly difficult to justify the expense and effort in a time of multiple crises. Such rationale and funding disparity needs correction, not least for self-preservation concerns of Climate, Food and the extensive extinction of Soil.

Arguments for coral reefs is predicated on the main claim that climate change is a major problem which may result in sea level rise and warmer waters – despite corals relying on both of these – while mainly failing to accept that any chance to address climate or pollution can only be achieved by fixing the Soil on land, on farms with our food choices.

While “Life in Soil” and Soil itself are strangely ignored in UN’s SDGs, **UN Sustainable Development Goal 14** for “Life below Water” that was advocated for by Ghislaine Maxwell, prior to her 2021 conviction, through her now-defunct non-profit, [The TerraMar Project](#). Fundamental flaws in all aspects of this Agenda are commented upon and corrected here - <https://vermecology.wordpress.com/2019/07/02/the-ocean-lies-still/> .

The Table below shows how Context and Triage are essential for making rational choices.

Table A1. Summary of Disparities in Relative Importance of the Major Realms of Life: viz. Land/Soil, Ocean and Freshwater, often mis-represented as having equal merit. Note that studies confirm Life originated in “*warm little ponds*” or geothermal pools on Land.

Ecological Realm Metrics	Soil/Land (% of total)	Ocean	Freshwater
Earth's surface area (+ terrain) Gha	>64 Gha (~65%)	36 (~35%)	0.5 (~1%)
Biodiversity/Species totals	~2.1x 10 ²⁴ (>99.9%)	10 ¹⁰	<10 ¹⁰
Total species known (Spp % Approx)	<0.00001%	>10%	~70%?
Extinctions on IUCN Redlist Spp	>910 (>90%)	2–4 (0.2%)	~100 (9%)
Living Biomass/Carbon Gt C	~2,500 (>99%)	3	0.3?
Living Phytomass/Carbon Gt C	~2,400 (>99.9%)	0.08	0.08?
Organic carbon store Gt C	30,000 (>99%)	<1,000	2,500 (soil)
Productivity NPP Gt C/yr	220–270 (~90%)	15–30	1.3
Human food Calories %	>99%	<1.5%	<1.5%
Freshwater store %	>70%	0%	<30%
O2 release from NPP/yr %	>99%	0–1%	<1%
Antibiotic/Anticancer/Drugs source	>50–60%	<0.1%	0?
Ecological Services value \$T/yr (%)	150 (>99%)	3	<0.3?
Floods/Fires, etc. events/yr (%)	>400 (100%)	-	-
Urban/infrastructure area %	~1–2%	-	-
Agriculture (on habitable area) %	~50%	-	-
Land/soil degraded by humans	30–66% (33% prime)	-	-
Organically farmed area	1%	-	-
Recent Acidification pH (% change)	-1.25–5.0 (>10,000%)	-0.1 (30%)	-0.3 (90%)
Plastic pollution Mt/yr	82 (>90%)	1.7 (0.5%)	7 (9%)
Dedicated Eco Research Institutes	0 (0%)	>900?	90
Ecological Research funding \$\$/yr	1%?	90%?	9%?

Information in this Table may be sourced or checked; comments/corrections welcomed.